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A study for location of store-based retail in urban areas : A case study of
Apparel market areas in Kanpur

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Bachelors' in Planning

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**A study for location of store-based retail in urban areas :
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*Thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the award of the degree of*

Bachelors in Planning

By
Adarsh Tripathi
2013BPLN011

Under the Guidance of
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&
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**SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE, BHOPAL
NEELBAD ROAD, BHOURI BHOPAL (MP)-462 030**

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Department of Planning
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Declaration

I **Adarsh Tripathi, Scholar No. 2013BPLN011** hereby declare that the thesis entitled “**A study for location of store-based retail in urban areas: A case study of Apparel market areas in Kanpur**” submitted by me in partial fulfilment for the award of Bachelor of Planning in School of Planning and Architecture Bhopal, India, is a record of bonafide work carried out by me. The matter embodied in this thesis has not been submitted to any other University or Institute for the award of any degree or diploma.

Adarsh Tripathi

Certificate

This is to certify that the declaration of **Adarsh Tripathi** is true to the best of my knowledge and that the student has worked for one semester in preparing this thesis.

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Executive summary

Since the last quarter of 20th century, Globalization emerged as an important phenomenon across the world because of its exponential growth and taking over many countries. It calls for trade of products and services from any part of world to another part in a smooth way. This provides investors an opportunity to invest in new emerging markets and economies. Retail is one of the biggest investment sector showing immense potential. For a systematic investment and recovery framework, it needs to be organized. Organized retail can also be categorized into various types in which store-based retail pops out as a major one. It is globally accepted that Indian markets has a huge potential for investment because of its unique demographic profile of nearly 1.3 billion people. Earlier Indian economy was closed and due to lack of huge investment opportunities, Indian markets were led by informal/unorganized sector. Indian economic reforms took place on 1991 which opened paths for investment opportunities in India.

With over 92 percent of the business coming from unorganized sector, Indian retail sector offers immense potential for growth and consolidation. The revenue generation from organized retail was INR 0.9 trillion (USD15.5 Billion) in 2009, INR 2.4trillion (USD41.4 billion) in 2012, and is expected to continuously growing at an impressive rate to a projected INR 5.5 trillion (USD94.8billion) by 2019. (KPMG, 2014)

Indian economy is drastically changed from the era of economic reforms which took place more than 25 years ago. There are many demand and supply factors which are presently leading the direction of Indian markets. But the success of a retail store cannot be completely articulated from these factors. From various decades of studies, it is found that location is the most important factor for articulating the success or failure of a retail store. A store's location is one of the most important decisions a retailer must make, as it typically involves substantial financial outlay and long-term commitment.

Location is a major cost factor-

- It involves large capital investment.
- It affects transportation cost.

- It affects Human resource cost.

Location is a major revenue factor-

- The volume of business depends on location.
- A prime location gives advantage over Competitors.
- It effects the consumers' traffic.

In previous years, a growing interest can be seen among the academic world and the private organizations for using GIS techniques in the investigation and planning of retail stores network. Almost all the various retail establishments have felt the need to plan for approaching consumer markets and compete with established competitions.

Aim of the study

Aim of the study is to identify suitable location for retail stores in urban area.

Objectives of the study

Objective 1:

To ascertain the factors for choosing retail store location by the retailers.

Research question 1: What factors do retailers consider when making a location selection decision in India?

Research Question 2: What coping strategies do retailers use?

Objective 2:

To select relevant indicators for identifying suitable retail location in Indian cities.

Research Question 3: How various techniques can be used as an effective tool for locating a retail store in most efficient way?

Objective 3:

To develop a framework for analyzing suitable location for retail store.

Scope and Limitations:

The scope of this study is to understand the techniques that retailers use to locate a potential site for a new store. The study will be carried out for organized sector

of retail. It will be followed by identifying suitable indicators and techniques which can be universalized for cities in India.

- Study is limited to organized retail sector in India.
- Study is limited to store-based retail sector.
- Study is limited to tier-2 cities which are emerging markets in Indian economy

Outcome:

The outcome of this study will be a GIS based framework which can be replicated into various Tier-2 cities for selection of a retail site.

Methods of data collection and analysis:

Study area for this study is Kanpur metropolitan area, U.P. It is labelled as the commercial hub of the state. It has a million plus population (27.61 lakh persons, as per 2011 census of India) which generates a huge demand for new products. Kanpur was established as a commercial and industrial hub by British. Kanpur is located along NH-2 (Delhi-Kolkata highway) which is proposed to be developed as DFC (direct freight corridor).

For this study 4 major apparel markets were selected in the city. These 4 apparel markets are- Generalganj, Naveen market, Sisamau, Govind nagar. These 4 major markets are assumed to be the representation of all of the rest small apparel markets in the city.

Literature review helped to identify the major factors which influence the location selection decision. These factors are- 1.) Market factors and, 2.) Operative factors

These factors are further categorized into various parameters and variables of study. These variables (both qualitative and quantitative) were collected through primary and secondary survey.

Data collection process includes both primary and secondary survey. Sampling strategy used for the primary survey was random sampling method. Sampling size was calculated to be 385 with the help of population size residing in study market area wards. Primary survey was emphasized on consumers' survey (270 samples) and shopkeepers' survey (115 samples). Some expert meetings were also organized with trade union leaders and planning officers of city to understand the market behavior and shoppers' perspective. Shopkeepers' survey focused on the problems faced by shopkeepers while taking location selection decision in India and the strategies/techniques they follow for location selection decision. Shopkeepers' survey was conducted to fulfill the 1st objective of study. With the help of literature review and 1st objective, path for completion of 2nd objective is to be carved.

In the shopkeepers' survey, problems faced by shopkeepers were categorized into 4 types- 1.) Unavailability of loading/unloading space, 2.) No parking facility, 3.) Unavailability of competitive space, 4.) Insufficient competitive prices. After analyzing the sample data it was found that nearly 60% of shopkeepers' identified

unavailability of loading/unloading space and parking space as the major problem they face in the existing market areas. While major strategies suggested by shopkeepers are- customer choices, vicinity of market areas, vicinity of residential areas and other. Most of the retailers agreed that they prefer customer choices and vicinity of existing market area as the strategic parameters over other parameters.

Consumers' survey was focused to gather the socio-economic and demographic character of population residing in the study area. It was also helpful to draw behavioral insights of consumers' towards apparel shopping in the study area markets. Consumers' survey focused on the distance travelled by consumers for apparel shopping, monthly frequency of shopping and suggested nearest location for new retail development (if any).

In the consumers' survey, it was found that nearly 88% of consumers have to travel minimum 3-5 km. and beyond distance for shopping purpose which is usually secondary and tertiary trade areas. It should be reduced to primary trade area (1km.buffer).

In the consumers' survey it was also found that nearly 57% of consumers do shopping on a monthly basis.

In the consumers' survey it was also found that a major share of consumers(nearly 30%) prefer Sisamau market because of its very well connectivity with both public and private transport. After Sisamau market, people prefer Naveen market (nearly 25%) because of on-street parking facility available there.

Scatterplot diagram was plotted to distinguish the relation between consumers' frequency and distance travelled. It was found that as the distance travelled by the consumers' increases then, their shopping frequency decreases.

Scatterplot diagram was also plotted to distinguish the relation between consumers' average monthly spending on shopping vs distance travelled. It was found that as the distance travelled increase the average expenditure also increases. It is because consumers want to save the travelling costs for next time.

According to U.P. Dookan aur Vanijya Adhistan Act, 1962 , a shop having 1-5 employees should pay 200 ₹ per financial year as registration fee to local body.

Secondary survey included the review of existing master plan of Kanpur city to understand current landuse pattern across the city and circle rates around the city. Other received reports and experts survey meetings were helpful to understand the background of apparel market in the city.

Analyzed and collected data was further analyzed in ArcMap 10.4. ArcMap 10.4 is the most essential tool used in the study for further analysis. With the help of collected data and defined variables, 4 analysis maps were prepared for further analysis. These 4 maps are landuse map, circle rates map, trade area buffer maps and thiessen (population) polygon map. These maps were prepared with the help of collected and analyzed quantitative data.

Landuse map was prepared with the help of available master plan document, with a highlight to the existing commercial areas. Circle rates map was developed with the help of circle rates handbook received from Kanpur development authority. Circle rates map is helpful for retailers to select most affordable available land area during the location selection decision. Thiessen (population) polygon map was prepared with the help of population density which was collected ward wise and then population density share was distributed among the 4 study area markets of the city. Thiessen polygon map was prepared with the “create thiessen polygon” function, where study area markets were selected as fixed points of distribution and limits were taken as municipal limits. Thiessen polygon map shows the individual population distribution shared by 4 study markets. Trade area buffer map was prepared by taking buffers of 1 km. (primary trade area), 3 km. (secondary trade area) and 5 km. (tertiary trade area) and beyond. Trade area buffer map was prepared with the help of multipolygon function in ArcMap.

After preparing all 4 types of maps, weighted overlay analysis is done by giving weights to different variables under the prepared map raster. Weighted overlay analysis is a tool in ArcMap which allows users to solve multi-criteria problems such as site selection and suitability models. It is done by inputting the reclassified values in the input rasters into a common evaluation scale of preference. The output from weighted overlay analysis is map which shows the potential of a land in an area for establishing new retail stores. There are 4 categories defined to show

potential of land- highest potential, moderate potential, least potential and restricted.

Retailers can choose areas from highest potential to moderate potential for further micro level location selection decision. Now qualitative factors like parking facility, rental cost, operating costs, availability of competitive space are helpful for retailer to prioritize the land. The land, fulfilling most of the priorities of the shopkeepers' should be selected as the final micro level decision.

Studies of this kind should not be done from retailers' perspective only but the major focus is to develop and suggest some planning interventions, which will be helpful for planning commercial areas and retails in the developing cities.

कार्यकारी सारांश

२०वीं शताब्दी के अंतिम चतुर्थांश में वैश्वीकरण एक महत्वपूर्ण कारक के रूप में उभरा है और उसका स्पष्ट कारण है इसकी अतिशय प्रगति और ये कई राष्ट्रों में भी प्रभावशाली है। इसका तात्पर्य पूरे विश्व भर में वस्तुओं और सेवाओं के आसान आदान-प्रदान से है। इसके द्वारा निवेशकों को नए उभरते हुए बाजारों में निवेश का अवसर मिला है। खुदरा / फुटकर व्यापार ऐसा ही एक महत्वपूर्ण निवेश क्षेत्र है जहाँ पर विकास की अत्यधिक सम्भावनायें हैं। अतः व्यवस्थित निवेश और निवेश-उगाही संरचना के विकास के लिये इसका औपचारिक तरीके से व्यवस्थित होना आवश्यक है। संगठित खुदरा को भी विभिन्न प्रकारों में वर्गीकृत किया जा सकता है जिसमें स्टोर-आधारित खुदरा एक प्रमुख व्यक्ति के रूप में फैला है। विश्व स्तर पर स्वीकार किया जाता है कि भारतीय बाजारों में करीब 1.3 अरब लोगों की अपनी अद्वितीय जनसांख्यिकीय प्रोफ़ाइल के कारण निवेश की एक बड़ी संभावना है। इससे पहले भारतीय अर्थव्यवस्था बंद थी और भारी निवेश के अवसरों की कमी के कारण, भारतीय बाजारों में अनौपचारिक / असंगठित क्षेत्र का नेतृत्व किया गया था। 1991 में भारतीय आर्थिक सुधार हुआ था जो भारत में निवेश के अवसरों के लिए मार्ग खोला था।

असंगठित क्षेत्र से आने वाले 92% से अधिक व्यापार के साथ, भारतीय रिटेल सेक्टर विकास और समेकन के लिए बहुत अधिक क्षमता प्रदान करता है। वर्ष 2012 में संगठित खुदरा क्षेत्र में राजस्व उत्पन्न 0.9 लाख करोड़ ₹ (USD15.5 अरब) थी, 2012 में ₹ 2.4 लाख करोड़ (USD 41.4 बिलियन), और अनुमानित 2019 तक ₹ 5.5 लाख करोड़ (USD94 बिलियन) में अनुमानित दर से लगातार बढ़ने की उम्मीद है।

25 वर्ष से अधिक समय पहले हुई आर्थिक सुधारों के युग से भारतीय अर्थव्यवस्था में काफी बदलाव आया है। कई मांग और आपूर्ति कारक हैं जो वर्तमान में भारतीय बाजारों की दिशा में अग्रणी हैं। लेकिन खुदरा स्टोर की सफलता इन कारकों से पूरी तरह स्पष्ट नहीं हो सकती। अध्ययन के विभिन्न दशकों से, यह पाया गया कि खुदरा स्टोर की सफलता या असफलता को व्यक्त करने के लिए स्थान सबसे महत्वपूर्ण कारक है। एक स्टोर का स्थान फुटकर बिक्री के लिए सबसे महत्वपूर्ण निर्णयों में से एक है, क्योंकि इसमें आमतौर पर पर्याप्त वित्तीय परिव्यय और दीर्घकालिक प्रतिबद्धता शामिल है। पिछले वर्षों में, बढ़ती रुचि को शैक्षणिक दुनिया में देखा जा सकता है और रिटेल स्टोर्स की जांच और योजना में जीआईएस तकनीकों का उपयोग करने के लिए निजी संगठन और लगभग सभी

विभिन्न खुदरा प्रतिष्ठानों ने उपभोक्ता बाजारों के आने और स्थापित प्रतियोगिताओं के साथ प्रतिस्पर्धा करने की योजना की आवश्यकता महसूस की है।

अध्ययन का उद्देश्य

अध्ययन का उद्देश्य शहरी क्षेत्र में खुदरा दुकानों के लिए उपयुक्त स्थान की पहचान करना है।

अध्ययन का लक्ष्य

लक्ष्य 1:

खुदरा विक्रेताओं द्वारा खुदरा स्टोर स्थान चुनने के लिए कारकों का पता लगाने के लिए।

शोध प्रश्न 1: भारत में एक स्थान चयन निर्णय पर खुदरा विक्रेताओं क्या कारण बताते हैं ?

अनुसंधान प्रश्न 2: खुदरा विक्रेताओं को क्या मुकाबला करने की रणनीतियों का इस्तेमाल होता है?

लक्ष्य 2:

भारतीय शहरों में उपयुक्त खुदरा स्थान की पहचान करने के लिए प्रासंगिक संकेतकों का चयन करने के लिए विभिन्न तकनीकों का उपयोग कैसे किया जा सकता है ।

शोध प्रश्न 3: विभिन्न तकनीकों का उपयोग सबसे प्रभावी तरीके से एक खुदरा स्टोर का पता लगाने के प्रभावी उपकरण के रूप में कैसे किया जा सकता है

लक्ष्य 3:

खुदरा स्टोर के लिए उपयुक्त स्थान का विश्लेषण करने के लिए एक ढांचा विकसित करना

क्षेत्र और सीमाएं:

इस अध्ययन का दायरा उन तकनीकों को समझना है जो खुदरा विक्रेताओं का पता लगाने के लिए उपयोग करते हैं । एक नई दुकान के लिए संभावित साइट अध्ययन खुदरा के संगठित क्षेत्र के लिए किया जाएगा। इसके बाद उपयुक्त संकेतकों और तकनीकों की पहचान कर सकते हैं जो कि भारत में शहरों के लिए सार्वभौमिक हो सकते हैं।

डेटा संग्रह और विश्लेषण के तरीके:

इस अध्ययन के लिए अध्ययन क्षेत्र कानपुर मेट्रोपॉलिटन एरिया, यू.पी. है। इसे राज्य के व्यावसायिक केंद्र के रूप में चिह्नित किया गया है। इसकी आबादी दस लाख से अधिक है (27.61 लाख लोग, भारत की 2011 की जनगणना के अनुसार) जो नए उत्पादों के लिए भारी मांग पैदा करता है। कानपुर को ब्रिटिश द्वारा एक वाणिज्यिक और औद्योगिक केंद्र के रूप में स्थापित किया गया था। कानपुर एनएच -2 (दिल्ली-कोलकाता राजमार्ग) पर स्थित है, जिसे डीएफसी (सीधी फ्रेट कॉरिडोर) के रूप में विकसित करने का प्रस्ताव है। इस अध्ययन के लिए शहर में 4 प्रमुख परिधान बाजारों का चयन किया गया। ये 4 परिधान बाजार- जनरलगंज, नवीन बाजार, सीसामऊ, गोविंद नगर हैं। इन 4 प्रमुख बाजारों को शहर के बाकी सभी छोटे परिधान बाजारों के प्रतिनिधित्व के रूप में माना गया है।

साहित्य समीक्षा ने प्रमुख कारकों की पहचान करने में मदद की जो स्थान चयन को प्रभावित करते हैं। ये कारक हैं- 1.) बाजार कारक और, 2.) उपगोणित कारक

इन कारकों को आगे अध्ययन के विभिन्न मानकों और चर में वर्गीकृत किया गया है। इन चर (गुणात्मक और मात्रात्मक दोनों) को संपूर्ण प्राथमिक और माध्यमिक सर्वेक्षण एकत्रित किया गया था।

डेटा संग्रहण प्रक्रिया में प्राथमिक और द्वितीयक सर्वेक्षण दोनों शामिल हैं। प्राथमिक सर्वेक्षण के लिए प्रयुक्त नमूनाकरण रणनीति यादृच्छिक नमूना पद्धति थी। अध्ययन बाजार क्षेत्र के वार्डों में रहने वाले आबादी आकार की सहायता से सैंपलिंग आकार की गणना 383 हो गई थी। उपभोक्ता सर्वेक्षण और दुकानदार सर्वेक्षण पर प्राथमिक सर्वेक्षण पर जोर दिया गया। बाजार के व्यवहार और दुकानदारों के परिप्रेक्ष्य को समझने के लिए ट्रेड यूनियन के नेताओं और शहर के नियोजन अधिकारियों के साथ कुछ विशेषज्ञ बैठकों का भी आयोजन किया गया। दुकानदारों के सर्वेक्षण दुकानदारों द्वारा सामना की गई समस्याओं पर ध्यान केंद्रित करते हुए भारत में स्थान चयन निर्णय लेने और स्थान चयन निर्णय के लिए वे रणनीति / तकनीक का पालन करते हैं। अध्ययन के प्रथम उद्देश्य को पूरा करने के लिए दुकानदारों का सर्वेक्षण किया गया। साहित्य की समीक्षा और प्रथम उद्देश्य की सहायता से, दूसरे उद्देश्य को पूरा करने का मार्ग तैयार किया जाना है।

दुकानदार के सर्वेक्षण में, दुकानदारों द्वारा सामना की गई समस्याओं को 4 में वर्गीकृत किया गया प्रकार- 1.) लोडिंग / उतराई स्थान की अनुपलब्धता, 2.) कोई पार्किंग सुविधा नहीं, 3.) प्रतिस्पर्धी अंतरिक्ष की अनुपलब्धता, 4.) अपर्याप्त प्रतिस्पर्धी कीमतों।

नमूना आंकड़ों के विश्लेषण के बाद यह पाया गया कि लगभग 60% दुकानदारों ने मौजूदा बाजार क्षेत्रों में बड़ी समस्या के रूप में लोडिंग / अनलोडिंग स्पेस और पार्किंग स्पेस की अनुपलब्धता की पहचान की। दुकानदारों द्वारा सुझाए गए प्रमुख रणनीतियों में - ग्राहक विकल्प, बाजार क्षेत्रों के आसपास, आवासीय क्षेत्रों के आसपास और अन्य थीं। ज्यादातर खुदरा विक्रेताओं ने सहमति व्यक्त की कि वे ग्राहकों की पसंद और वर्तमान बाजार क्षेत्र के आस-पास क्षेत्र को दूसरे मानदंडों पर रणनीतिक मापदंडों के रूप में पसंद करते हैं।

उपभोक्ता सर्वेक्षण सामाजिक-आर्थिक और जनसांख्यिकीय को इकट्ठा करने के लिए केंद्रित था। अध्ययन क्षेत्र के बाजारों में परिधान खरीदारी के प्रति उपभोक्ताओं के व्यवहार संबंधी अंतर्दृष्टि को आकर्षित करने के लिए यह भी सहायक था। उपभोक्ताओं के सर्वेक्षण ने परिधान खरीदारी के लिए उपभोक्ताओं द्वारा खरीदारी की मासिक आवृत्ति की दूरी पर ध्यान केंद्रित किया और नए खुदरा विकास के लिए निकटतम स्थान का सुझाव दिया।

उपभोक्ताओं के सर्वेक्षण में, यह पाया गया कि लगभग 88% उपभोक्ताओं को यात्रा करना पड़ता है। न्यूनतम 3-5 किमी और खरीदारी के प्रयोजन के लिए दूरी से परे है जो आमतौर पर द्वितीयक और तृतीयक व्यापार क्षेत्रों है। इसे प्राथमिक व्यापार क्षेत्र (1 किमी. बफर) में घटाया जाना चाहिए।

उपभोक्ताओं के सर्वेक्षण में यह भी पाया गया कि लगभग 57% उपभोक्ता मासिक आधार पर खरीदारी करते हैं। उपभोक्ताओं के सर्वेक्षण में यह भी पाया गया कि उपभोक्ताओं (लगभग 30%) का एक बड़ा हिस्सा सीसामऊ बाजार को पसंद करता है क्योंकि सार्वजनिक और निजी परिवहन दोनों के साथ इसकी बहुत अच्छी तरह से कनेक्टिविटी है। सीसामऊ बाजार के बाद, वहां पर सड़क पार्किंग सुविधा के कारण लोगों को नवीन बाजार (लगभग 25%) पसंद है।

स्कैटरप्लॉट आरेख को उपभोक्ताओं की आवृत्ति और दूरी की यात्रा के बीच के संबंध में अंतर करने के लिए प्लॉट किया गया था। यह पाया गया कि उपभोक्ताओं की बढ़ती दूरी के कारण, उनकी खरीदारी की आवृत्ति कम हो जाती है। स्कैटरप्लॉट आरेख को उपभोक्ताओं के औसत के बीच के अंतर को अलग करने के लिए भी प्लॉट किया गया था। खरीदारी बनाम दूरी पर मासिक खर्च कूच किया यह पाया गया कि दूरी के रूप में औसत वृद्धि की यात्रा की। व्यय भी बढ़ता है इसका कारण यह है कि उपभोक्ताओं को अगली बार यात्रा की लागतों को बचा जाना है।

माध्यमिक सर्वेक्षण में कानपुर शहर की मौजूदा मास्टर प्लान की समीक्षा शामिल है। शहर के चारों ओर शहर में मौजूदा भूमिगत पैटर्न और सर्कल दरों को समझें शहर में कपड़ों के बाजार की पृष्ठभूमि को समझने के लिए अन्य प्राप्त रिपोर्ट और विशेषज्ञों की सर्वेक्षण बैठकें सहायक थीं।

ArcMap 10.4 में विश्लेषित और एकत्र किए गए डेटा का विश्लेषण किया गया था। ArcMap 10.4 आगे के विश्लेषण के लिए अध्ययन में प्रयुक्त सबसे आवश्यक उपकरण है। एकत्रित आंकड़ों और परिभाषित चर की सहायता से, आगे विश्लेषण के लिए 4 विश्लेषण नक्शे तैयार किए गए थे। ये 4 नक्शे भूमि का नक्शा, सर्कल रेड्स मैप, ट्रेड एरिया बफर मैप्स और थिसेन (जनसंख्या) बहुभुज का नक्शा हैं। ये मानचित्र एकत्रित और मात्रात्मक डेटा का विश्लेषण करने के साथ तैयार किए गए थे।

लैंडयूज नक्शा उपलब्ध मास्टर प्लान दस्तावेज की सहायता से तैयार की गई थी, जिसमें से एक मौजूदा वाणिज्यिक क्षेत्रों पर तथा सर्किल दरें नक्शा कानपुर विकास प्राधिकरण से प्राप्त सर्कल रेट पुस्तिका की मदद से विकसित किया गया था। सर्कल दरें नक्शा खुदरा विक्रेताओं के लिए स्थान चयन निर्णय के दौरान सबसे सस्ती उपलब्ध भूमि क्षेत्र का चयन करने के लिए उपयोगी है। थिसेन (आबादी) बहुभुज का नक्शा जनसंख्या घनत्व की सहायता से तैयार किया गया था जिसे वार्ड वार किया गया था और फिर शहर के 4 अध्ययन क्षेत्र के बाजारों में जनसंख्या घनत्व का हिस्सा वितरित किया गया था। थिसेन बहुभुज का नक्शा "थिएसेन बहुभुज" आदेश के साथ तैयार किया गया था, जहां अध्ययन क्षेत्र के बाजारों को वितरण के निश्चित बिंदु के रूप में चुना गया था और सीमाएं नगरपालिका सीमा के रूप में ली गई थीं। थिसेन बहुभुज का नक्शा 4 अध्ययन बाजारों द्वारा साझा की जाने वाली व्यक्तिगत आबादी वितरण को दर्शाता है। व्यापार क्षेत्र बफर नक्शा 1 किमी के बफर्स ले जाकर तैयार किया गया था। (प्राथमिक व्यापार क्षेत्र), 3 किमी (माध्यमिक व्यापार क्षेत्र) और 5 किमी (तृतीयक व्यापार क्षेत्र) और परे ट्रेड क्षेत्र बफर मानचित्र आर्कपाक में बहुपंजीगत आदेश की मदद से तैयार किया गया था।

सभी 4 प्रकार के नक्शे तैयार करने के बाद, वेटेड ओवरले विश्लेषण तैयार नक्शा रेखापुंज के तहत विभिन्न चर के लिए वजन देकर किया जाता है। वेटेड ओवरले विश्लेषण ArcMap में एक उपकरण है जो उपयोगकर्ताओं को साइट चयन और उपयुक्तता मॉडल जैसे बहु-मानदंड समस्याओं को हल करने की अनुमति देता है। इसे इनपुट रैस्टर में पुनर्वित्त मूल्यों को वरीयता के एक सामान्य मूल्यांकन स्तर में इनपुट करके किया जाता है। भारत ओवरले विश्लेषण से उत्पादन एक नक्शा है जो नए खुदरा दुकानों की स्थापना के लिए किसी क्षेत्र में किसी भूमि की क्षमता को दर्शाता है। भूमि की

क्षमता दिखाने के लिए 4 श्रेणियां परिभाषित की गई हैं- उच्चतम क्षमता, मध्यम क्षमता, कम से कम संभावित और प्रतिबंधित।

रिटेलर्स अधिक सूक्ष्म स्तर के स्थान चयन निर्णय के लिए उच्चतम क्षमता से लेकर मध्यम तक संभावित क्षेत्रों को चुन सकते हैं। अब पार्किंग सुविधा, किराये की लागत, परिचालन लागत, प्रतियोगी अंतरिक्ष की उपलब्धता जैसे गुणात्मक कारक, भूमि को प्राथमिकता देने के लिए फुटकर विक्रेता के लिए सहायक हैं। दुकानदारों की प्राथमिकताओं को पूरा करने वाली भूमि को अंतिम सूक्ष्म स्तर निर्णय के रूप में चुना जाना चाहिए।

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In the last decade, global investors have been driven by market-centric factors over efficiency-centric factors while choosing investment destination. Many Large international retailers and MNCs' are continuously increasing their presence in new countries, particularly in emerging markets due to their high growth potential.

Despite certain characteristic challenges the Indian retailing landscape is very dynamic and India's twin-growth engines, economic liberalization and demographic profile set it apart from other nations and presents a convincing business case to global retailers seeking to enter the market.

With over 92 percent of the business coming from unorganized sector, Indian retail sector offers immense potential for growth and consolidation. The revenue generation from organized retail was INR 0.9 trillion (USD15.5 Billion) in 2009, INR 2.4trillion (USD41.4 billion) in 2012, and is expected to continuously growing at an impressive rate to a projected INR 5.5 trillion (USD94.8billion) by 2019. (KPMG, 2014)

Keywords & definitions: Retail, economic liberalization, unorganized sector

Retail: The part of a country's economy that is made up of businesses that sell goods through stores to the public. (Cambridge, 2016)

Economic liberalization: "Economic liberalization incorporates the processes, including government policies that promote free trade, deregulation, abolition of subsidies, price controls and rationing systems, and, often, the downsizing or privatization of public services." (United Nations, 2010)

Unorganized sector: "Consisting of all independent private enterprises owned by individuals or households engaged in the sale or production of goods and services operated on a proprietary or partnership basis and with less than ten total workers." (Sector, 2008)

1.2 Importance of location

A store's location is one of the most important decisions a retailer must make, as it typically involves substantial financial outlay and long-term commitment. Given

the importance of the decision, it is not surprising that site location has been studied (in retailing, marketing, and related disciplines) since the early 1900s. (Applebaum, 1965)

As noted by (Craig, 1984) in a special edition of the *Journal of Retailing* devoted to locational analysis, “the choice of a store’s location is perhaps the single most important decision a retailer has to make... even slight differences in location can have a significant impact on market share and profitability”. Recent changes in the retail landscape make the continued study of retailer site selection a worthwhile pursuit. (Mejia, 2002)

In previous years, a growing interest can be seen among the academic world and the private organizations for using GIS techniques in the investigation and planning of retail stores network. Almost all the various retail establishments have felt the need to plan for approaching consumer markets and compete with established competitions. For few past decades the methods used for study of identifying the locations of retail stores have become more complex and clear as a result of relevant modeling techniques which are developed with GIS (Duggal, 2007).

According to the industry’s trade group, shopping centers can be classified into nine categories including six well-established formats (regional and super regional shopping malls, convenience shopping centers, neighborhood shopping centers, community shopping centers, and outlet centers) and three newer formats (power centers, theme/festival centers, and lifestyle centers). Faced with the current retail crash and an expanding set of location options, a well-chosen site may mean the difference between success and failure of retailers.

1.3 Problem statement

India as an emerging market has a huge potential for development of retail sector. A vast range of demand and supply factors are also leading for increasing economy in retail sector. “The Indian retail industry has emerged as one of the most dynamic and fast-paced industries due to the entry of several new players. It accounts for over 10 per cent of the country’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and around 8 per cent of the employment. India is the world’s fifth-largest global destination in the retail space” (India Brand Equity Foundation, 2016).

In Sector profile of Indian retail sector, FICCI also projects an optimistic future. The most important factor in growth of India's retail sector is the scale of growing middle class which is estimated to increase from 21 million households today to 91 million households in 2030. According to FICCI "High end growing level of domestic consumption of products is another supporting factor projected to contribute in potential growth of India's retail sector. India's present consumption level which presently is US\$ 750 billion may get double within five years to US\$ 1.5 trillion. Thus, India's huge population with large proportion of young population, high potential growth in consumer spending, the macro trends for the sector look favorable" (FICCI, 2011).

Table 1: Demand and Supply Factors for new retail

<u>Demand Factors</u>	<u>Supply Factors</u>
• Growing Youth segment and working woman population	• Rapid real estate infrastructure development
• Rising incomes and increasing purchasing power	• Easier access to credit
• Higher brand consciousness	• Increased efficiency due to development in the supply chain
• Changing customer preferences and growing urbanization	• R&D, innovation and new product development
• Increasing number of HNI's(High net worth individuals)	• Growing interest of investors
• Rising internet penetration	• Conducive regulatory environment due to expected reforms

Source: (KPMG, 2014)

The above stated demand and supply factors create a scope for an emerging market. Changing customer preferences and rising purchasing power demand for better & more retail stores. This will also lead to establishment of many international firms opening retail stores in India. Increasing no. of retail stores will lead to the competition of location which can tap more customers & generate more revenue than others.

1.4 Need for Study

LOCATION IS A MAJOR COST FACTOR-

- **It involves large capital investment.** A location used for locating a new store is usually bought or leased for a long duration. So it needs an involvement of one-time large capital investment. Prime locations for commercial stores are available at a higher rent.
- **It affects transportation cost.** A store which is located near to major transport nodes saves a major share of transportation cost. Cost of transporting increases as far as the store is located from transport nodes.

- **It affects Human resource cost.** Easy availability of cheap labour in the vicinity of store location can be very helpful for reducing costs borne on human resources for store.

LOCATION IS A MAJOR REVENUE FACTOR-

- **It effects the customer traffic.** A store located in a prime location attracts greater customer traffic than a store located in an unusual location. As a result it helps for revenue increase of the store.
- **The volume of business depends on location.** A store located near dense areas attracts more business which is directly connected to revenue generation.
- **A prime location gives advantage over Competitors.**

1.5 Aim of the study

Aim of the study is to identify suitable location for retail stores in urban area.

1.6 Objectives of the study

Objective 1:

To ascertain the factors for choosing retail store location by the retailers.

Research question 1: What factors do retailers consider when making a location selection decision in India?

Research Question 2: What coping strategies do retailers use?

Objective 2:

To select relevant indicators for identifying suitable retail location in Indian cities.

Research Question 3: How various techniques can be used as an effective tool for locating a retail store in most efficient way?

Objective 3:

To develop a framework for analyzing suitable location for retail store.

1.7 Scope and Limitations:

The scope of this study is to understand the techniques that retailers use to locate a potential site for a new store. The study will be carried out for organized sector

of retail. It will be followed by identifying suitable indicators and techniques which can be universalized for cities in India.

- Study is limited to organized retail sector in India.
- Study is limited to store-based retail sector.
- Study is limited to tier-2 cities which are emerging markets in Indian economy

1.8 Outcome:

The outcome of this study will be a GIS based framework which can be replicated into various Tier-2 cities for selection of a retail site.

1.9 Study area:

The study area for this study is Kanpur metropolitan area. It is devised as the commercial hub of Uttar Pradesh. Kanpur was established by British rule as a cantonment for control over a large area in North India. It was further developed to become an industrial and commercial trade centre of north India. Due to its development it attracted a huge population migration in search of employment opportunities which made it one of the most populous city of the country. Kanpur was earlier known as “Manchester of the East” because of many textile mills and leather industries located here. The establishment of these industries needed a market nearby for maximum profit by saving transportation cost. So new apparel markets were developed by British for providing local employment opportunities.

1.9.1 Characteristics of study area:

Kanpur metropolitan sprawling over an area of 260 Sq. kms. is the biggest city and main centre of commercial, industrial and educational activities in the State of Uttar Pradesh. It is an ancient city between Ganga & Pandu Rivers and is strategically placed at the centre of Uttar Pradesh with good rail and road connectivity. Important roads like NH-2 (Kolkata-Delhi), NH-91 (Kanpur-Kannauj-Etah- Aligarh-Delhi), NH-86 (Kanpur-Mahoba-Bhopal-Indore) & SH-58 (Kanpur-Lucknow) connect Kanpur to important cities in Uttar Pradesh and across the country. Kanpur is one of important railway junctions for northern line (Kanpur- Delhi) as well as trunk line (Kanpur-Lucknow). According to the census 2011, Kanpur city has a population of 27.61 lakhs, municipal area is administratively divided into 6 zones and 110 wards. (Census of India, 2011)

Figure 1: Map of Kanpur Nagar Nigam (Source: Kanpur Development Authority)

1.9.2 Selection Criteria

- a) Kanpur is labeled as commercial capital of state U.P.
- b) Kanpur is a million plus city and a major destination of migrants in U.P. and nearby states.
- c) Kanpur is linked with all prominent cities and towns of U.P. and other states of India via roadways and railways.
- d) Kanpur is located on eastern DFC (Amritsar-Kolkata highway) which is major industrial corridor in India.
- e) Kanpur is selected to be developed under “Smart city” project by Gol.
- f) Huge upper and middle class population provides strong demand base for regional economy.

1.10 Methodology:

Method to be used for this study will be Trade area analysis method. Among the retailers, the concept of Trade Area analysis is one of the most interesting and popular method because it allows them to study and understand the business potential and the competition in market with other retailers. In earlier days, Trade Area analysis was limited to irregular estimates and mental calculations. With

manual calculations the analysts often supposed that people usually travel in straight lines, instead of using actual distance or traveling time. With GIS related methods it is possible to handle big data amounts, with great precision and speed.

Recently, some of the retail location analyses have attempted to improve the limitations of assuming noncircular trade areas by describing the trade areas into primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas and even drawn Thiessen polygons to divide the space with a given arrangement of retailers available in markets.

1.10.1 Data Preparation

The study will be done to observe the spatial patterns and distribution of retail stores which are present in the study area. In this study there will be an extensive use of GIS and statistical analysis techniques as a tool of data preparation and analysis. With the help of built-up blocks and other building related data, the Data layers will be prepared in ArcMap. Data related to socio-demographic profile of area will be collected from Census of India and some primary survey if required. Some data related to stores will be collected from primary survey and rest with help of secondary survey

Variables to be used in the study are-

1. Socio-economic/Demographic
2. Non-demographic/Spatial
3. Site Specific (pertaining to respective retail store)
4. Retail inter-store competition
5. Store Specific (pertaining to respective retail store)

Table 2: Variables to be used for analysis¹

Types of Variables	Description	Examples
Socio-economic/Demographic	Secondary data based variables meant to capture the level of demand in the retail trade area	Number of households, population density, average income, education, dwellings ownership
Non- demographic and spatial	Typically non-demographic attributes of the influence area surrounding the retail trade	Average daily traffic counts, distance to nearest public transportation stop, percent of retail land use within 1 mile
Site Specific (pertaining to respective retail store)	Numerical or categorical description of the relative attractiveness of respective retail store	Site features (freestanding, mall etc.) size of store, visibility, design/ aesthetic, store image
Retail inter-store competition	Variables characterizing how much competition is associated with a particular store	Number of primary & secondary competitors, amount of competitive space with comparison to respective competitor, spatial alignment of respective stores with respect to the location
Store Specific (pertaining to respective retail store)	Attributes of store which are in direct control of management	Index of store management quality, number of staff, number of counters active

¹ Variables which are defined in the table may vary according to the character of site .

Figure 3: Methodology Chart

1.10.2 Geocoding

Geocoding is the method that translates physical addresses to point locations on the street network. There are various types of address formats which one can apply for Geocoding by matching the store no. and its location (e.g.: street numbers) in the referenced street database. In this study, the location of retail stores will be geocoded using their addresses available. Geocoding merges the available map information with street addresses to locate a point individually on a base map for each related address.

1.10.3 Geoprocessing

Geoprocessing includes various analysis processes by pre-defined algorithms. Geoprocessing of the Geocoded data helps for catchment area or store influence area analysis.

Buffer Analysis

Buffer analysis tool defines a new class of buffer polygons around the geocoded stores. Created buffers are studied in Euclidean space and they use a 2-d platform. These buffer polygons allow us to study that how these polygons are related to the success or failure of the stores. The buffer function generates concentric polygons by encircling a point with a buffer width. Geometric buffers are applied for various spatial analyses in GIS.

For trade area analysis, concentric circles of 1 mile, 2 mile and 5 mile radius are drawn along the store. These circles are known as primary, secondary and tertiary trade area respectively.

Thiessen Polygon

Thiessen polygons which are also popularly known as Voronoi polygons, represent the influence areas around a set of focal points (or retail outlets as in this study). Thiessen polygons are drawn in a way that one polygon covers only one store and any point/location within the polygon is equally close to the store (centroid) than to any other store. Thiessen polygons are drawn with the help of perpendicular bisectors between neighboring points.

Overlay Analysis in GIS

Overlay Analysis tool in GIS is used to add-up weights to various data inputs and then merges them into a single data output. It applies a mutual set/scale of values to different and unrelated data input to produce a unified data analysis. Overlay analysis merges all the attributes of the shapes provided in the overlay analysis to create a new unified polygon.

1.10.4 Regression Analysis

Thiessen polygons or Voronoi polygons are used to symbolize of store influence/trade areas. With the help of Voronoi polygons one can easily summarize the various features related to socio-economic and other demographic attributes for a specific retail store. Regression is a statistical technique which is used for calculating the scale of appearing changes in the outcome of dependent variable while there is a change in the value of one or more independent variables.

While using regression analysis, researcher seeks to establish the mutual effects of variables upon another—the effect of a price increase upon demand, for example, or the effect of changes in the money supply upon the inflation rate. To explore such issues, the investigator assembles data on the underlying variables of interest and employs regression to estimate the quantitative effect of the causal variables upon the variable that they influence. The investigator also typically assesses the “statistical significance” of the estimated relationships, that is, the degree of confidence that the true relationship is close to the estimated relationship. (Skyles, 2000)

The changes in values of dependent variables in relation with independent variables as linear mathematical function can be easily explained by Linear regression analysis. Single variable linear regression function is used where in a linear relationship is analyzed between one dependent variable and one independent variable. In multiple regression function the relationship involves more than one independent variables. This multivariable linear regression function relationship is described as:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_i X_i + \dots + \beta_p X_p + e_i$$

Where: -

Y = the value of the i^{th} case of the dependent scale variable

β_i = regression coefficient,

$i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p$

X_i = the i^{th} predictor

e_i = disturbance term

The rationality of the regression function is examined by the value of the coefficient of determination R^2 . When regression models are tested with a hypothesis of no significance then it is known as null hypothesis. This is explained as-

$$H_0: R^2 = 0$$

Which means that the changes in the values of the dependent variable does not have a statistical relationship with the changes in the values of independent variables. After testing the value of R^2 , it is possible to check the importance of the model/proposed parameters. This analysis would include the regression coefficients and the error term (constant). The concepts of this statistical testing would also follow the same general format as that of the hypothesis for testing R^2 .

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

Store location theory has a rich and old history, with early works produced in geography dating back to the 1930s when thought leaders such as Christaller sought to identify a theory which could be used to explain the market level location decisions of business proprietors. Adding to the depth of the earlier literature was an inflow of ideas from complementary disciplines which relaxed some of the stringent assumptions of the early theories and made it possible to explore location planning from an individual store perspective, rather than a market perspective.

There are three basic types of locations available for retail stores:

1. Solitary sites,
2. Unplanned shopping areas and
3. Planned shopping districts.

1. Solitary Sites (Free-Standing Sites, Isolated Sites)

This type of location relates to single, free standing outlets that are isolated from other retailers. They can be positioned on roads or near other retailers or shopping centers. Such sites are used, for instance, by large store formats in food and non-food retailing or for convenience shops.

2. Unplanned Shopping Areas

Unplanned shopping areas are retail locations with several outlets in close proximity to each other that have evolved over time. The retail mix is not the result of long range planning and for such locations there is no centralized management.

The main kinds of unplanned shopping areas are

- a) Central business districts (traditional “downtown” areas in cities/towns),
- b) Secondary business districts in larger cities and main street or high street locations in smaller cities,
- c) Neighbourhood districts, and
- d) Strip or string locations (locations along a street or motorway).

3. Planned Shopping Districts/Shopping Centres

Planned shopping areas are retail locations that have been architecturally planned to provide a unified theme for a number of outlets. These sites are developed deliberately and usually have some large, key retail brand stores and a number of smaller retailers to add diversity and special interest.

Retail Location Decision Process

Retail location decisions follow a systematic process that starts with a general assessment of geographic areas and leads to a detailed assessment of specific site characteristics.

This process can broadly be described as a three step selection process:

1. Market selection: The first step is the concern of a region that has potential for a new retail outlet.

2. Area analysis: Within the chosen region, a potentially ideal area for the store is selected.

3. Site evaluation: In the chosen geographical area, the best available site(s) are examined in terms of all features that are relevant to probable store performance. This step concludes with a final decision as to the specific site.

Today, site selection literature can be found throughout a diverse mix of academic disciplines such as marketing, geography, economics, psychology, operations research, urban planning, architecture, transportation, and real estate management.

First, macro-level theories are explicated with particular attention paid to the seminal works of Christaller and Hotelling. The second section transitions into work at the micro level where the studies focus on individual site selection decisions rather than the more global marketplace forces. This section explores the vast array of ways that site selection has been theorized, studied, and applied.

During the past decades, there are various developments seen in the field of spatial-data analysis, data storage and mapping. GIS have been very advantageous in challenging spatial analytic approaches and developing an edge in the field of location sciences.

2.1 Macro-Level Location Planning

Earlier attempts for retail location planning strategies can be seen from 1930s. The earliest literature for location planning theory comes from Christaller and Hotelling. Earlier researchers and academicians tried to explore the macro-level approaches that describe location choices of business proprietors in a particular market. These theories do not predict the exact locations that businesses will choose; instead, they examine “the aggregate decisions of a heterogeneous group of retailers” (C. Samuel, 1984) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011) .

Christaller’s central place theory is the most famous theory of all the location theories available in present world. The ideas of this theory suggest, in accord with popular economic theory of the time, that goods and services are largely commodities with few observable differences and that consumers make rational choices to buy from the place (store) offering the lowest price. Because the goods or services were viewed as commodities, prices were unlikely to vary much from one shopkeeper to another. The only differential cost to the consumer was the cost of travel to the various retailers. Because the theory assumes that consumers are equally spaced within the market, stores will logically be positioned in such a way that “the shape of each market area is hexagonal, and a range of adjacent hexagons define the totality of market areas” (Eppli, 1994) .

With further modifications in central place theory, Losch acknowledged that real prices paid by consumers increase with distance. Using microeconomic theory to explain the resulting spatial patterning of retailers, Losch theorized that quantity demanded must decrease with corresponding increases in distance. “ When distance is neglected, economic areas overlap; that is, they are too far extended on the one hand, and shot through with holes on the other” (Losch, 1954) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). The most theoretically sound trade area for each retailer could be described in terms of a spatial demand cones, derived from the differences in demand due to distance. “From this cone, the firm’s total sales in a spatial market can be calculated,” and an economically viable location could be selected “whose total sales, as determined by the volume of the spatial demand cone, provide an adequate rate of return” (Craig, 1984).

The Pioneer in the field of literature related to retail location theories was Harold Hotelling. Hotelling suggested that buyers are not always completely rational and do not always search out the lowest price for a given good or service. Buyers may continue to frequent a particular shopkeeper despite higher prices “because they live closer to his store than to the others, or because they have less shipping to pay from his warehouse to their own, or because his mode of doing business is more to their liking, or because he sells other articles which they desire, or on account of some difference in service or quality, or for a combination of reasons” (Hotelling, 1929) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011).

The collective customer irrationality creates an incentive for retailers to cluster together, with each differentiating the goods or services sold just enough to attract for the “new commodity as many buyers of the old as possible, to get, so to speak, between one’s competitors and a mass of customers” (Hotelling, 1929) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). The result is a market where all competitors cluster together in order to capture an equal share of the market. Most famous examples of this theory can be seen as the clothiers of Oxford Street in London, the theaters of Broadway, and the casinos of Las Vegas.

Reilly’s law of retail gravitation explains the agglomeration of competitors at one place. Reilly’s law advocates that the trade area of two competing areas/towns will be in same proportion which proportion lies between their populations. Further shopping centers, rather than towns, have become the perspective for the theory.

As the population of one town (or the size of one shopping center) increases in relation to the size of the other, the trade area of the larger town (or shopping center) expands and encompasses a larger portion of the available market. This occurs because more consumers are drawn to the convenience associated with multi-purpose. According to Reilly, retailers (both competing and complementary) mass together in order to take advantage of the increased perceived attractiveness by the consumer (Nelson, 1958) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011).

2.2 Micro-Level Location Planning

Micro-level location planning is a subset of Macro-level location planning. Once a market/area is denoted as a potential site then Micro-level site planning should be taken into consideration to find an ideal location for establishing a new store. In this

stage the retailer is faced with the task of choosing an actual site for their store within the more broadly defined region or market. Retailers must take into consideration a lot of organizational and site specific factors to arrive at a decision regarding potential store sites. “The approach taken for it and the choice of the factors considered may vary from one retailer to the next” (Applebaum, 1965) . At this level, the location planning theories suggested by central place theory or Reilly’s law of retail gravitation do not provide guidance, as the focus shifts from macro-level to micro-level analysis .

2.2.1 Practitioner’s method for selection of retail site

Although there are various approaches used by retailers but three common and easily-applied approaches to site selection are often used by retailers:

- The analogue approach,
- The checklist method and,
- Regression models

Analogue Method:

Analogue method was one of the most common and sophisticated method used as a practitioner’s approach for finding an ideal location of stores. This method was advocated by Applebaum in the early 1960s. It involves identifying stores that are similar to the one which is proposed. Similarity of the stores is identified on the basis of “empirical measurements of store sales in relation to known market factors, consumer shopping behavior patterns and store characteristics” (Applebaum, 1966).

The trade areas of these stores are then examined and used as guides for the potential volume of sales that could be expected at the proposed location, subject to adjustments made to account for significant differences in the site or store characteristics (Applebaum, 1965) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). This method like others have several important drawbacks, including bias in selecting comparable stores, the indirect testing of competition (Craig, 1984) and the need for a large number of potential stores to serve as similarities.

Checklist Method:

The most upfront method for selection of location of site is the use of checklists to compare prospective sites. Checklists came into popularity in the late 1950s. Nelson in "*The Selection of Retail Locations*", recommended retailers to first collect a catalog of potential sites and then systematically grade each using a retail location checklist. Nelson's checklist covered eight key areas:

- adequacy of the potential trading area,
- the accessibility of the site within the trading area,
- The trade area's growth potential,
- The potential to intercept business,
- The potential for shared business,
- Shopper turnover,
- Location of competition, and
- Site cost-to-productivity estimates.

After scoring for each site, using particular responses in ordinal scale, the sites with the lowest scoring are rejected and the remaining sites are subjected to more detailed analysis regarding "business volume and the projection of possibilities for future growth" (Nelson, 1958) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). Checklist method is still popular method among retailers for selection of potential sites.

Regression Models:

The most popular and used approach to site selection is the use of regression models. This approach came into light in the early 1970s. Using multiple regression techniques on existing stores, researchers are able to methodically examine the relationship between various site characteristics and the corresponding sales or profit levels. A typical regression model predicts sales volume as a linear function of location, store characteristics, market attributes, price, and competition (Craig, 1984).

For application of regression models the data may be gathered using publicly available sources and proprietary information relating to stores within the retailer's chain. One advantage of the regression approach is that the importance of the various elements used in the model can be revealed through estimated beta

weights, which alert retailers of the potential importance of factors that may be of particular consequence in their industry. For example, a bank considering a new branch may find that it is extremely important to have ample free private parking for its clients, whereas a hair salon may find that location of complementary businesses is more important.

Regression approaches are not, however, without their drawbacks. First, it is nearly impossible to include all relevant variables. To overlook the impact of variables and overlapping of similar functions change the expected outcome of analysis.

It is important to note that different types of retailers view the site location process from very different viewpoints. Therefore, the factors that are considered (or modeled) vary quite a bit. Differences have been uncovered for retailers of varying size, with larger retailers (defined as those operating more locations) utilizing more, and often more complex, site selection techniques than smaller retailers (Hernandez, 2000).

Hernandez and Bennison found that grocery retailers used a greater variety of techniques than did retailers specializing in home improvement, books/music, fashion and accessories, or department stores. A final defining characteristic driving the site selection process is the retailer's corporate culture. As Hernandez and Bennison note, the majority of retailers "have yet to adopt the more sophisticated approaches, particularly the knowledge-based ones, and the reasons for this may lie primarily in the internal culture of the company" (Hernandez, 2000).

2.2.2 Academic approaches for selection of retail site

For the selection of a potential retail site Academic approaches typically develop different methodologies than the approaches used by practitioners, although examples can be found of both the analogue and regression models in the academic literature.

Many of the theoretical models "evaluate locations at the market area or trading area level and involve the simultaneous selection of facility locations and the transfer of demand to those locations in order to optimize some specified criteria" (Craig, 1984). These criteria might involve optimizing the revenue of a single store or the revenue of an entire arrangement of stores. So while the focus of the

practitioner's models was on reducing the number of potential sites in order to pick one "best" location, the goal of these location allocation models is typically larger in scope and involves finding the location or locations with the highest projected sales volumes.

Early work in this field was conducted by Huff whose model claimed to capture "the dynamic aspects of location in the retail field" (Huff, 1966). Huff's model, and others based on it, rely on store size and distance characteristics to determine the optimal location of a store. Generally Huff's model is used to select a location for an additional outlet within a chain, the allocation model also includes a measure reduction of demand for each store in the chain as consumers migrate to the new store (Kelly, 1993).

Huff's model have been criticized for a number of reasons. One major issue is that it was designed to add only one incremental store to an established configuration. Ignoring between-store interactions often resulted in location decisions that identified near optimal individual locations but failed to identify an ideal system of stores.

Location analysis models have historically been underutilized due to their complexity and the scarcity of software capable of carrying out the analysis (Lea, 1991) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). Recent research, however, suggests that there has been "a switch in emphasis in locational strategy from a preoccupation with new development towards a more holistic approach to the management of store portfolios" (Hernandez, 2000). Location allocation strategies are therefore likely to gain in favor as this site selection method evaluates the retail environment with a wider scope.

A major reason for criticism of location allocation models is that they oversimplify the variables that consumers consider when choosing which store to visit for a given need. In his early research, Huff acknowledged the deficiencies of his approach, stating "decision-makers should be aware that there are variables other than those specified in the model that affect sales of a retail store...Therefore, it is important that supplemental techniques for appraising the site be used in conjunction with the general sales estimates afforded by the model" (Huff, 1966).

“ The understanding that spatial choice models must consider other attributes in addition to distance led a number of authors to propose consumer utility functions which included both locational and non-locational factors;” the resulting models are commonly referred to as gravity or spatial interaction models (Craig, 1984).

The Multiplicative Competitive Interactive (MCI) model is perhaps the most recognized of the gravity models (Craig, 1984) and provides the foundation for many empirical tests of gravity (Mejia, 2002) . In the MCI model, both size and image are incorporated into a linear function that is estimated using log transformations and least squares techniques, thereby overcoming parameter estimation problems associated with earlier efforts to model the interactive effects of the spatial and non-spatial factors affecting store performance (Nakanishi, 1974).

Applications of the MCI model recognize interactive effects of size and image (Mejia, 2002). In 1984, Nevin and Houston discovered that it is the image of a preferred store within a shopping center, rather than the distance to the center, that is most important in determining where consumers choose to shop. These studies suggest that stores with strong positive images “can draw customers from greater distances to shop at a specific center and in the process create a significant demand externality for the non-anchor occupiers in the center through the increased consumer flow” (Eppli, 1994).

2.2.3 Selection of independent variables

Regardless of the approach used, “all systematic site evaluation methods require clearly defined independent or explanatory variables” (Lea, 1989). Unfortunately, the literature rarely provides an example of a case similar enough in order to serve as an example for practitioners. Instead, retailers and/or analysts must use their knowledge, previous experience, and familiarity with any location methods being used to determine which variables to include in a particular site location decision.

Both practitioners and academics tend to use a large number of socioeconomic and demographic variables in site selection methods because this information is relatively inexpensive and easy to obtain (Lea, 1989). However, none of the commonly used methods rely solely on these types of variables. Nelson’s much acclaimed checklist system incorporated variables from all but the store specific

class and Applebaum's analogue procedure utilized variables from all five classes which are - Socioeconomic/Demographic, Situation of site within broader geography, Site, Competition, Store.

Regression models utilize variables from the same set as do checklist and analogue approaches. Common variables include population size and socioeconomic characteristics, store specific factors such as local promotion and advertising, and data on the competitive environment (Craig, 1984). Location allocation models, on the other hand, usually incorporate fewer variables. Huffs model contains variables relating to the number and size of competitors, the size of potential sites, the number, income, and product expenditures of nearby households; and the distance from the households to the various sites. The restricted scope of the variables used in location allocation models is often cited as one of the drawbacks to the approach (Eppli, 1994).

Gravity models' minimum data requirements far exceed any of the site location methods and often include variables related to "demand regions (location, amount of demand), retail sites (location, attractiveness, type), distances between origins and sites, and an observed flow between origins and destinations," (Lea, 1990) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011). Gathering the required measures of flow and attractiveness often involves time consuming and costly surveys.

2.2.4 Consumer Preferences of Shopping Locations

Although limited, this literature stream is crucial as it serves to document the importance of locational elements on the choices that consumers make when deciding where to shop. Turley and Milliman recognize the importance of the retail site on shopper behavior stating that the site "is the first set of cues normally seen by a consumer...[and] must be pleasing and induce approach behaviors for a retail store or service to be successful" (Turley, 2000).

A recent empirical investigation of consumer choice among shopping options available in downtown business districts, open air lifestyle centers, and traditional enclosed shopping malls discovered that significant differences do exist in the perceptions of and behaviors toward these distinct location types, with distance and image of the retail location type being important determinants of choice (Yan, 2009).

Convenience, which has been defined in the services literature as “consumers’ time and effort perceptions related to buying or using a service,” influences satisfaction (Berry, 2002).

A convenient, well-regarded site thus can become a formidable advantage for a retailer.

2.3 Identifying Overlap in the Literature

When comparing literature in the areas of micro-level site selection, macro-level site selection and consumer choice of shopping venue, the overlap in constructs employed becomes apparent. Micro-level site selection literature commonly incorporates variables from up to five categories (socioeconomic/ demographic, situation, site, competition, and store specific) to guide retailers’ site selection decisions (Lea, 1989) as quoted by (Fowler, 2011).

Milliman and (Turley, 2000) suggest that locational factors tied to convenience/distance, image, and physical attributes of the shopping center impact not only shopper perceptions but also shopper patronage and shopping frequency. These constructs correlate very closely with the situation, site, and store specific variables used in the micro-level site selection literature. The importance of socioeconomic / demographic variables to the study of consumer choice behavior is somewhat less straightforward.

To be successful, retailers must consider and accommodate consumer preferences to attract shoppers. Therefore, if consumers choose among shopping destinations based on convenience, distance, image, and/or physical attributes of the location, then retailers must provide stores that are close, convenient, and offer appropriate images and physical attributes. Thus, micro-level site selection theories can benefit from the insights gleaned from research investigating how consumers choose among retail outlets.

2.4 Modern GIS based Approaches

During the past decades, several important advancements have taken place in remote sensing and mapping. “Geographic Information Systems have been very useful in tackling spatial analytic approaches and in forming an interface with the

field of location science” (Church, 2002). Many studies put emphasis on the topic that GIS can be used in terms of development and various methods that can be used for land-use suitability modeling.

GIS can be used to collect and analyze large volumes of data from various sources with different scales and in different co-ordinate systems. “GIS can combine and simultaneously use several databases by transforming them into a common set of database” (Pullar, 1999). The use of GIS and remote sensing involves the aspect of accuracy of representing real world situations in a GIS database (Church, 2002).

2.4.1 GIS as a tool for Retail Location Decision

“The competitive nature of retail environment and the large number of techniques used by the retailers has led GIS to be one of the prime application for optimum retail location” (Davies, 1994).

GIS has contributed in improving the efficiency and precision of retail store location planning. The methodologies which were used for identifying optimum retail store location now have become more complex and accurate as a result of modeling procedures brought about by GIS (Birkin M., 1996).

There are various applications which are developed with help of GIS, can be used to identify an optimum location. Some of them are Probability Density Function (PDF), Decision Support Systems (DSS), Spatial Interaction Models, Network Huff Model, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) (Byrom, 2005), RASTT (Retail Aggregate Space Time Trip Model) (Baker, 2002).

“The Network Huff Model is formulated on GIS with the method of the network of shortest-path method as an extension of the ordinary Huff which was earlier based on Euclidean distance” (Okabe, 2001). New Huff network method can be used for identifying the demand of retail stores on a street network in a given area. The Huff model use distances between retail stores to estimate divisions of the entire market area into various singular trade influence areas of the retail stores.

This method approaches to identify the scale of spatial patterns, the relationship between the size and function of retail stores. Retailers are now using GIS as decision-making tool for long-term strategies.

Thiessen trade area models have been also used to produce retail influence areas based upon store specialties and consumer requirements. “Thiessen diagram models are used for identifying trade areas for a set of similar stores in an area” (Jones, 1993). This method is also useful in those studies where detailed consumer patronage data is unavailable or difficult to acquire. “Thiessen polygons can be used to identify the impact and changes of the existing set of facilities, as well as identify potential sites for new facilities” (Ghosh, 1987).

The general Thiessen diagram assumes the location of the stores and assumes that the consumers patronize the nearest store (Ghosh, 1987). The second method is the multiple weighted Thiessen polygons. The multi-weighted Voronoi diagram (MWVD) identifies at both locational as well as non-locational factors. Voronoi diagrams are used to discuss the locational distribution of stores in space. Voronoi diagrams have also been used to minimize the average travel time and average travel cost to the nearest stores.

Figure 4: Voronoi Polygon (source: GIS Stackexchange)

2.5 Analysis of Trade Areas

According to the available literature, various researches in academia have also identified some other methods which can be used for identifying retail influence areas. These methods have been classified into the following categories:

1. Simple methods for trade area analysis
2. Gravitational methods for trade analysis

2.5.1 Simple methods for trade area analysis

William Applebaum was the pioneer in this field. To develop the organized retail forecasting model based on empirical data he invented the analog method in 1932. This method is generally used by retailers and consulting firms to measure the performance features of existing stores in order to forecast sales at new sites. The analog method is non-geographic and is often implemented by regression analysis.

“Proximal Area Method is a geographic approach for delineating trade areas which assumes that consumers choose the nearest store to visit among the similar kind of outlets” (Ghosh, 1987). This method applies the assumptions that customers also consider minimum travel distance and time while selecting or patronizing a store. “Once the trade area is defined, the store sales can be projected by analyzing demographic variables and spending habits of the perspective customers” (Wang, 2006).

2.5.2 Gravitational Methods for Trade Analysis

The consumer based approach looks for the nearest store location in relation to the consumers. The store based approach constructs Thiessen polygons around each store in order to define the proximal area. To obtain consumer information, Thiessen polygon can be overlaid by demographic variables. This method considers the distance and time traveled to delineate trade areas. There are other similar methodologies have been developed in academia that consider distances (or time) and attraction of stores. One of the most popular technique that is generally used to delineate retail-trading areas is the law of retail gravitation.

The Distance from city B to the breakup point of the retail trade area between two cities =

$$D_{BP} = \frac{\text{Distance between City a and b}}{1 + \sqrt{\frac{\text{population b}}{\text{population a}}}}$$

Where: A and B are the cities.

Reilly's law of retail gravitation is generally used for identifying the zones, where the retail store is getting its patronage. An alternative model is based on the hypothesis that the probability of a customer offered a set of alternatives, selecting a particular item/service is directly proportional to the perceived utility of each alternative. This model can be used for predicting consumer spatial behavior, delineating trade areas, locating retail and service facilities, analyzing market performance and forecasting sales, etc.

2.6 Theoretical framework

With the help of available literature many theories and frameworks are crafted by various firms and academia working in the field of retail and trade. Many theoretical and functional frameworks are advised by international firms for various potential locations for big shopping stores and malls however there is a lack in the field retail location related theories and models. The reason behind it is the ignorance of retail studies while comparing the scale of studies for malls and shopping centres available.

The third and last objective of this study is to develop a framework which can be replicated into various Indian cities showing somewhat similar characteristics. Indeed, the high location sensitivity of the retail sector is one of its most prominent features (Öner, 2014). With transactions often requiring face-to-face interactions and, "consumption and production of retail services [often taking] place in very close proximity (Öner, 2014)," retail establishments tend to be found within or near regional centers (Öner, 2014).

This study required data related to retail sector in the city. This data was distributed among various categories. These categories included data collection from consumers (based on primary survey), data collection from shopkeepers (based on primary survey), data from Municipal corporation or local governing body (for services provided to existing markets and other charges and fees), Development

authority (for the proposed landuse and other charges and fees) and other agencies (includes which are directly or indirectly influencing retail market related to apparel sector in the city).

The study embraces various factors of study which lead to the parameters and variables of study. The factors are broadly categorized into two sections which are – Market factors (includes all the variables excluding operating factors) and Operating factors (all the costs and other services which are involved in operating a store). The parameters are identified which subcategorizing the factors. They can vary from place to place according to the socio-economic, geographical and other characteristics of the city. While further variables are identified by subsection of identified parameters. They can also vary from place to place similar to parameters.

2.6.1 Market Factors

Market factors are the factors which are influencing the store attraction from the consumer side. Albeit they play the most important role for deciding the success or failure of store in any specific location. Market factors are the factors which include

consumers, competition, nearby available services, surrounding population and spending habits of consumers. These factors are involved in implications for store attractions. These market factors are helpful for predicting the success of store in the market.

Market factors can be subdivided into various parameters. For study purpose market factors were categorized into 3 sub-sections.

- 1.) Market factors related to consumers
- 2.) Market factors related to other facilities
- 3.) Market factors related to competitors

2.6.1.1 Market factors relating to consumers

Market factors relating to consumers majorly focuses on a store's location in relation to the socio-economic and demographic structure of the area surrounding. It may be a small area as a ward or large as a city wide approach. Retailors pay a special attention to it while searching for potential store location in new areas.

It takes after that potential areas ought to be evaluated on both the amount and the nature of the population inside their given market range. From one viewpoint, amount includes populace density; increments in population density will, every single other component staying consistent, result in expanded buyer and products demand in the area. Then again, the nature of customers in a region includes statistic (socio-demographic) and financial (economic) structures. Socio-demographic represents all the variables, including salary, age, sex etc. which provides the data expected to decide if the encompassing shopper body is harmonious with the retailer's intended interest group; presumably no factors are more critical to retail supervisors than the statistic and socio-demographic structure of the market in any potential area.

Furthermore, the purchasing tendencies for the customer body – when, where, how and how regularly they shop – are additionally commanding variables to consider. The financial structure of a range is firmly identified with its socio-demographic structure and incorporates such variables as, household income, purchasing power and consumers' ability to spend for shopping purpose. Ranges in household

income must be considered as retailers offering high request products pull in more clients when situated in high-pay regions. As it were, buyers must be both willing and ready to purchase more products at the store.

Population density

Population density should be considered for all the areas city wide. Areas with higher population density can serve as a nearer market for huge population. In this way the areas with higher population density provide a good case to establish a store in that area or nearby places.

Spending habits and purchasing power

Spending habits and purchasing power also depend on the consumers in the surrounding areas. If the population of nearby areas are high earning then they also have a higher rate of purchasing power. It directly links with spending habits of consumers. During survey, it should be categorized into any of Daily/Weekly/Monthly/Quarterly/Yearly manner for the convenience.

2.6.1.2 Market factors relating to other facilities

Beyond the location in relation to consumers, a second set of market factors should be taken into consideration when assessing potential retail sites, namely those relating to the location of other (complementary) facilities. The location of a store in relation to recreational facilities, workplaces or stores selling complementary goods may increase retail attraction by taking advantage of the population flow generated by these sites and facilitating multipurpose shopping trips (González-Benito, 2005).

Locating retail stores near government buildings, educational institutions, or other non-retail establishments that attract large numbers of people potentially increases the number of customers that impulsively visit a retail store. In this way, retail firms not only directly attract consumers, but may see their market share increase by locating near retailers selling goods that consumers tend to buy during the same shopping trip, or near non-retail institutions that attract large numbers of people for a host of unrelated purposes. Conversely, high order good retailers located near certain types of land uses, such as industrial land, may experience adverse effects.

This type of measures decrease the average shopping distance travelled by consumers for shopping exclusively at a specific type of retail store.

Distance of market from residences

Distance of market from residences play a very important role for study. The higher the distance travelled by the consumers increases, the willingness to frequently visiting markets decreases in similar ratio.

Availability of Parking space

If a market area provides parking spaces for private vehicles then it attracts more consumers because it gives consumers an opportunity to directly reach market area without any barriers.

Availability of Public Transport

Availability of Public transport also plays an important role for consumers comfort to travel to the market areas. Public transport connects all the parts of city to other parts of city. It make market places much accessible to consumers.

2.6.1.3 Market factors relating to competitors

Besides location factors relating to consumers and complementary facilities, retailers should also assess a site's location in relation to competitors, as co-location implies overlapping market areas and, thus, sharing demand. This means that, "the selection of market areas with low competitor presence may be a key to success" (González-Benito, 2005). Also, as consumers may tend to choose which shopping area to visit before choosing a specific store, the location of new competitors may be lost on consumers when the number of stores within a shopping area passes a certain threshold. The result is the same level of demand now being distributed among a higher number of stores (González-Benito, 2005).

However, the spatial concentration of competing retailers can also have positive effects as it can serve to reduce the risk perceived by customers by facilitating searching for and comparing products between stores without a significant increase in travel costs. This reasoning is especially relevant for high-order, high-

implication shopping (also known as shopping goods) as consumers tend to prefer to compare different stores with regards to price, quality, and appearance when shopping for goods like clothing. Yet the desire for variety in repetitive shopping can also justify a spatial concentration of convenience good retailers (González-Benito, 2005).

2.6.2 Operative Factors

Whereas market factors are essential to the location decisions of retailers, the costs of opening and operating a store at a certain cannot be ignored. Operating factors are the factors which are involved in operating a location. Operating factors are usually financial factors. Operating factors can vary from one location to other effecting the location decision as the investment can differ in different location. Operative factors include registration cost, circle rate/rental cost of area, salaries and other store operating costs, loading/unloading costs if any applicable.

Assuming that retail store entrepreneurs primarily utilize apparel retail stores to stimulate brand awareness and loyalty in the short-term, the financial consequences would appear to be of less importance for traditional clothing chain retail stores. That being said, given the limited finances of many clothing retailers, operative factors cannot be said to be irrelevant.

2.7 Functional framework

The functional framework is developed with the help of theoretical framework. Functional framework includes all the steps which should be taken for identifying the potential store locations. The functional framework will be followed in the study in further chapters. In general, a framework is a real or conceptual structure intended to serve as a support or guide for the building of something that leads the research into something useful.

Theoretical framework includes all the parameters and variables of study. These variables of the study can be collected with primary and secondary surveys. Primary surveys include the Consumers survey and Shopkeepers survey and meetings with various stakeholders. Secondary survey data can be collected from Development authority, Municipality or other urban local body etc. Functional framework includes all the steps of arranging the data, analyzing the data and

attaining useful inferences from it. With the help of the analysis of the data various maps will be prepared. These maps will be further analyzed for identifying the potential location for retail stores in urban areas.

2.7.1 Data Collection

Data to be collected for study includes the parameters and variables identified for study. A checklist for data to be collected should be made before starting the data collection process. This checklist may vary according to the socio-demographic and economic characteristics of city. For data collection process, existing market places and nearby areas should be selected. There may be many markets identified in the city but the major ones should be selected which influences the citywide economics. This can be done as per user convenience. Data collection process can be done into two phases-

1. Primary data collection
2. Secondary data collection

2.7.1.1 Primary data collection process

Primary data collection process includes consumers' survey and shopkeepers' survey. Consumers' survey data includes majorly market factors and variables. These variables and parameters are spending habits of people, education level, distance travelled by consumers for market areas, frequency of travel, availability of parking spaces and availability of public transport from residential areas to market areas.

Shopkeepers' survey data includes the problems faced by shopkeepers in the existing markets. This articulates the existing market related problems and this can be helpful for establishing new areas where they will not have the similar problems. Shopkeepers' are experienced for projecting new places where the business/stores can be successful. The primary survey related to shopkeepers' should also include the factors or techniques they follow for identifying potential market areas. This indigenous knowledge can also be helpful for establishing parameters and variables. It can vary from the existing parameters and variables from literature review. This can be an advantage as it will give more effective results according to the variables which can be easily adapted for local to the city. Shopkeepers' survey can also be attributed with operative factors which include

rental costs or circle rate of area, operating costs at different market places and some other variables costs (e.g. registration cost and Loading/unloading costs etc.) which can be local to the markets. These operative factors may vary from place to place. They should be considered for analysis as they play a major role for shopkeepers’.

2.7.1.2 Secondary data collection process

Secondary data to be collected for the study is majorly data collected from various govt. offices and private firms or the various local unions or other locally established govt. /private bodies which play a vital role in market areas for the urban area. Secondary data includes the landuse guidelines for the city which are developed by development authorities. Other municipal boundaries and ward level boundaries and their population density and other data can be collected from municipality or the existing urban local body. Govt. offices which are related to market areas can also provide various reports made on citywide market areas. These reports can also be helpful for study. Meetings with local trade unions can be helpful to understand the market dynamics citywide. Secondary data plays a very important role to understand the background of market economics and various hidden but obvious variables which play important roles for existing market areas and proposed ones, if any.

2.7.2 Data analysis

Survey data analysis process is a multi-stage process. These processes are based on the variables for which data has been collected with help of primary and secondary survey. Inferences from these data analysis processes should be used for the study as they provide the insights of surveyed areas and population which may be helpful to cater the population citywide.

2.7.2.1 Primary data survey analysis

As mentioned above, primary data typically includes the survey done for consumers’ and shopkeepers’. These consumers’ survey gives the insights of the behavioral practices of consumers related to shopping. These behavioral practices includes the distance travelled by the consumers for shopping, frequency of shopping, their spending habits and other related variables.

The shopkeepers’ survey gives the insights of shopkeepers’ strategies for identifying new market areas and the problems they face in existing markets. With

the help of information provided by shopkeepers, the problems can be ranked in order to its influence which will make new market less prone to these problems. The strategies suggested by the shopkeepers can be helpful for combating these problems. Shopkeepers might be providing a huge information which can be irrelevant for the study. To resolve this problem, an earlier meeting should be placed with market unions to identify the major heads of study and survey should be done only these points/heads.

Identified variables from consumers' and shopkeepers' data can be helpful for defining the correlation of factor which are influencing the consumers' habits or the market dynamics. These correlations should be identified with the available data.

2.7.2.2 Secondary data analysis

Secondary data analysis can be iterated a literature review as it includes the landuse guidelines, reports from the govt. offices and other private firms which are working in the field. These guidelines are the major factors influencing the existing market areas and other related facilities. Secondary data is used to provide the base for method or techniques used in study.

2.7.3 Data analysis framework

Data analysis framework is developed with the survey data collected from the consumers' survey and shopkeepers' survey. The variables of study should be analyzed together for identifying the correlation among them. In this study, from the consumers' survey 3 major variables were identified to define the correlation among the variables. This will help to prepare maps in ArcMap. These maps will be further analyzed for identifying the potential location for commercial areas in city.

The variables identified from consumers' survey to study the correlation are – **Distance travelled by consumers for shopping, Shopping frequency, Average monthly spending²**. There were 2 different scenarios created while manipulating the distance travelled by the consumers. While the dependency of

² Average monthly spending here implies the average monthly amount of money spent by the consumers on apparels only. No other monthly commodity spending were accounted in survey.

shopping frequency and average monthly spending were assumed as depending variable for distance³ travelled as an independent variable.

Scenario 1: If the average distance travelled by the consumers' is more than 3 km. (secondary trade areas) then, impact on the shopping frequency of consumer and the average monthly spending.

Scenario 2: If the average distance travelled by the consumers' is less than 3 km. (secondary trade areas) then, impact on the shopping frequency of consumer and the average monthly spending.

Results from scenario 1 should be calculated as follows:

If, Distance travelled increases then, Shopping frequency decreases and average monthly spending increases.

Distance \propto (1/Shopping frequency) \propto Average monthly spending

Results from scenario 2 are as follows:

If, Distance travelled decreases then, Shopping frequency increases and average monthly spending increases.

Distance \propto Shopping frequency \propto Average monthly spending

These two scenarios should be analyzed for the collected consumers' data. The data collected should be accessed and the prominent scenario in the study area should be identified. Literature review suggests retail stores should be located near to residential areas. If it is found in the study that most of the consumers have to travel more than 3 km. and beyond which should be reduced. This will also increase revenue for retailers. It will be a win-win situation for both consumers' and retailers'.

2.7.3.1 Map preparation for analysis

This study is based on final data analysis in GIS based medium. The method is based on Thiessen trade area method. Thiessen polygons should be made according to the population distribution in the urban area. In this study there were

³ Distance are categorized in 3 categories – 1 km, 3 km., 5 km. for the convenience of survey as well as identifying the primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas.

4 major market areas were identified and the population distribution should be done for all the 4 markets covering complete city under their respective trade areas. Other different types of maps are to be generated with the help of data collected in primary and secondary surveys. The maps prepared for this study are –

1. Trade area buffer map for markets
2. Thiessen polygon (population) map
3. Landuse map of Kanpur Nagar (with existing master plan)
4. Circle rates map for city

Thiessen polygon map is to be prepared for distributing the population share citywide with respect to the existing market places' trade areas. This will show the population distribution share for existing study area markets.

Trade area buffer maps are created with the help of boundaries of existing market areas. These existing market boundaries should be drawn in Arcmap and other vicinity areas should be clearly identified before drawing it. The limits of primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas should be clearly defined. In this study, Primary trade area is identified as 1km. vicinity of market areas and likewise 3 km. for secondary trade areas and 5km. for tertiary trade areas from literature review.

Landuse map of the city can be prepared with the help of existing master plan of the city. The landuse map shows the predefined commercial spaces within city and its connectivity to other landuses. In this way the existing commercial area provide a base for other places where new commercial spaces will be viable and support the study.

Circle rates map can be prepared with the help of circle rates handbook from development authority or the municipality. This should also be prepared for the complete city areas and the land with moderate prices should be selected to give a higher ranking than land with very high cost. This reduces the operative factor variable land cost and make a new retail store more affordable for retailer.

These 4 maps are to be prepared for objectifying the social, economic and demographic form of all the areas city wide. Thiessen polygons represent the demographic profiled share of various areas as per the existing study market areas in the city. Trade area buffer maps are important to understand the share of

consumers in all 3 types of trade areas and likewise the competition can also be devised in qualitative nature (if needed). Landuse map shows the current prescribed use of land as per the urban local body. Circle rates map is prepared to show the land rates for all the areas. It influences the affordability of the retailer for any interested site in the city.

2.7.3.2 Weighted overlay analysis

Weighted overlay analysis tool applies one of the most used approaches for overlay analysis to solve multi-criteria problems such as site selection and suitability models. In a weighted overlay analysis, each of the general overlay analysis steps are followed. In weighted overlay analysis, you must define the problem, break the model into submodels, and identify the input layers.

The Weighted Overlay tool allows to implement several of the steps in the general overlay analysis process within a single tool. The tool combines the following steps:

- a) Reclassifies values in the input rasters into a common evaluation scale of suitability or preference, risk, or some similarly unifying scale
- b) Multiplies the cell values of each input raster by the rasters' weight of importance
- c) Adds the resulting cell values together to produce the output raster

The tool only accepts integer rasters as input, such as a raster of land use or soil types. Continuous (floating-point) rasters must be reclassified to integer before they can be used. The values of continuous rasters are grouped into ranges, such as for slope, or Euclidean distance outputs. Each range must be assigned a single value before it can be used in the Weighted Overlay tool.

The Reclassify tool allows for such rasters to be reclassified. You can either leave the value assigned to each range and assign weights to the cell values in the Weighted Overlay tool later, or you can assign weights at the time of reclassifying. With the correct evaluation scale chosen, simply add the raster to Weighted Overlay. The cells in the raster will already be set according to suitability or preference, risk, or some similarly unifying scale. The output rasters can be weighted by importance and added to produce an output raster.

2.7.4 Final site selection decision

With the help of weighted overlay analysis, the potential of a site is identified throughout the city. There are 4 categories defined for describing the potential of locations-

1. Highly potential area
2. Moderate potential area
3. Least potential area
4. Restricted/prohibited area

Retailors should choose the land from highly potential area and moderate potential area according to their priority. After selecting a locality falling under the highest and moderate potential areas, qualitative variables play important role for location selection decision at micro level. Some of these qualitative factors are registration cost, parking availability, rental cost, operating costs, loading/unloading costs (if any), availability of competitive space etc. There are many other qualitative variables which can vary from place to place. A retailer should keep all the preferred qualitative variables while making final selection decision. The location with highest potential should be selected as the final location of that specific retail store at micro level.

CHAPTER 3: STUDY AREA

3.1 Study Area Profile

Kanpur formerly known as Cawnpore, was established by British East India Company. Earlier it was a village named Kanhpur at the bank of holy river Ganga. Kanpur metropolitan sprawling over an area of 260 Sq. Kms. is the biggest city and main centre of commercial, industrial and educational activities in the State of Uttar Pradesh. It is an ancient city between Ganga & Pandu Rivers and is strategically placed at the centre of Uttar Pradesh with good rail and road connectivity. According to the census 2011, Kanpur city has a population of 27.61 lakhs, municipal area is administratively divided into 6 zones and 110 wards. Kanpur is one of the major Industrial towns in the country. It was very famous in the world for manufacturing of clothes and known as Manchester of Asia. After some time, most of the clothes manufacturing units were closed.

Figure 2: Location map showing Kanpur city in Indian Subcontinent (Source: (Kanpur, n.d.)

3.2 Land-use profile of city

Kanpur master plan is the legal document for assigning landuses for various areas in city. The major share of landuse is occupied by residential use with near to 41% but still it is less than the suggested share by UDPFI guidelines by MoUD. However the share of commercial area is just 2.61% which is way less than suggested 4-5% as per UDPFI guidelines. Share of Industrial Land-use is 5.55% which falls under the appropriate share as per suggestions of UDPFI guidelines.

Major share of Commercial activities is distributed among market areas. These markets are the hub of both local and regional economy as they cater both local and regional demand. Another factor for development of these concentrated markets is the proper railways and roadways connectivity of Kanpur with other major cities of India.

Table 3: Land Use as per Master plan, 2021

Landuse	Area(Hectare)	% share	UDPFI
Residential	14043	41.67	45.00-50.00
Commercial	879.99	2.61	4.00-5.00
Industrial	1871	5.55	5.00-7.00
Recreational	3221	9.56	16.00-20.00
Utilities	461	1.37	NA
Government	4668	13.85	NA
Transportation	3362	9.98	6.00-8.00
Others	3124	9.27	8.00-10.00
Total	33703.99	100%	100%

Source: Master Plan of Kanpur, 2021

Figure 3: Landuse map of Kanpur city

(Source: Master Plan of Kanpur, 2021)

3.3 Reasons for City selection

Preferably a city with high local and economic value was to be selected which shows high potential for growth of commercial sector in terms of local and regional economy. The case study area is Kanpur Municipal Corporation area, consisting of 6 zones and 160 wards. Kanpur is located on banks of river Ganges and plays an important role in state as well as national economy.

3.3.1 Fast Sprawling and urbanizing city

Kanpur is the most urbanized city of Uttar Pradesh. Kanpur city is growing rapidly and expanding into the countryside and on western side leading to the changes in land use pattern, morphological character and social and economic. In the fringe areas, rural character is gradually replaced by a more urban profile in terms of economic activities, land use, employment, income and culture.

3.3.2 Million plus city

Kanpur city has a population of 27.65 lakh and still growing. It also witness huge population influx or migration from various surrounding cities and states. This huge population growth needs new areas to be developed to cater sufficient services. Earlier British established fabric and leather industries helped to the growth of the city and huge population influx.

3.3.3 Commercial capital of Uttar Pradesh

Kanpur formerly known as “Manchester of India” is now labelled as the commercial capital of the state. According to Department of Economics and statistics, Uttar Pradesh, it is observed that the economy in terms of NSDP of Kanpur was increased from Rs. 8,233.32 crores in 2012-13 to Rs. 10,643.57 crores in 2015-16 resulting in a growth of economy of about 3.53 percent during the period.

3.3.4 Strategic location

The geographical advantage of the city will attract investment and business as Eastern DFC corridor (Amritsar-Kolkata) will pass through Kanpur and a logistic hub is planned at sub-urban area.

3.4 Study area characteristics

Study area has 4 sites within Kanpur Municipal Corporation. These four study areas are – Generalganj, Naveen market, Sisamau and Govind Nagar. Among these four study areas, three market areas are located near to the old parts of Kanpur city. Generalganj, Naveen market and Sisamau are older market areas which are pure commercial and mixed – commercial areas in nature. Govind Nagar is a newly established market area which is mixed-commercial in nature.

Generalganj is Kanpur's oldest market area. It was developed after British established cantonment in Kanpur. Generalganj is still one of the biggest apparel markets in Uttar Pradesh. Generalganj lies near to cantonment in the north of city of Kanpur. It is majorly commercial area with very narrow streets and lanes leading to the old city of Kanpur. Generalganj lies in ward no. 102 with very dense populated areas in nearby. The major road which connects other areas with Generalganj is Kanpur-Lucknow highway road.

Naveen market is considered as a posh market area in Kanpur because of high-end brand shops located here. Naveen market area is located near to Generalganj market area but shows a very different characteristic. Naveen market has wider streets and provides on-street parking to retailers and consumers. Naveen market is very well connected to other parts of city with both public and private transport.

Sisamau market is located near to the centre of Kanpur city. It is very well connected to all the areas of Kanpur city with public transport. There are shops ranging from cheap to very expensive apparels which makes it the most preferred shopping market of Kanpur city. Sisamau market is mixed- commercial area in nature because of nearby residential area. After independence of India, geographical expansion of the area took place towards the south and west of the Sisamau market area. Streets are usually congested because of illegal street parking and heavy pedestrian movement.

Govind nagar is located in the south of Kanpur city. It is also one of the most popular apparel market of the city because of its vicinity to most densely populated areas. It solely serves the southern part of city. It is also a mixed-commercial market area. It is located in ward no. 91 & 93. Kanpur city as always developed in southern direction due to the constraint of river Ganges in north. Govind nagar bears a huge share of population and area because of it.

Figure 4: Wards map of Kanpur Municipal Corporation

Source: Kanpur Municipal Corporation

Table 4: Market areas and their characteristics

Market	Nature	Wards	Population	Public transport	Parking
Generalganj	Commercial	102	25030	N	N
Naveen Market	Commercial	59	27687	Y	Y
Sisamau	Mixed-Commercial	41,50	39034	Y	N
Govind Nagar	Mixed-Commercial	93,98	47230	Y	N

Source: (Primary Survey and Census of India)

3.4.1 Study area 1: Generalganj

Generalganj is Kanpur's oldest market area. It was developed after British established cantonment in Kanpur. After some decades they developed Kanpur as a major industrial and commercial city in north India. Generalganj is still one of the biggest apparel markets in Uttar Pradesh. Generalganj lies near to cantonment in the north of city of Kanpur. It is majorly commercial area with very narrow streets and lanes leading to the old city of Kanpur. Generalganj lies in ward no. 102 with very dense populated areas in nearby. The major road which connects other areas with Generalganj is Kanpur-Lucknow highway road. It passes from the north of market areas and is major freight corridor connecting other major cities viz. Lucknow, Allahabad, Varanasi etc. Because of narrow streets and lanes, Generalganj is the most congested market area in Kanpur.

Figure 5: Shopping street in Generalganj

Source: Primary Survey

3.4.2 Study area 2: Naveen market

Naveen market is considered as a posh market area in Kanpur because of high-end brand shops located here. Naveen market area is located near to Generalganj market area but shows a very different characteristic. Naveen market has wider streets and provides on-street parking to retailers and consumers. Naveen market is very well connected to other parts of city with both public and private transport. Kanpur Development Authority has launched a redevelopment project to redevelop the Naveen market area. It was under the redevelopment process during the survey period.

Figure 8: Naveen market earlier

Source: *Primary survey*

Study Area

Figure 9: Naveen market (in present redevelopment phase)

Source: Primary survey

Figure 10: Naveen market (proposed development)

Source: Kanpur Development Authority

3.4.3 Study area 3: Sisamau

Sisamau market is located near to the centre of Kanpur city. It is very well connected to all the areas of Kanpur city with public transport. There are shops ranging from cheap to very expensive apparels which makes it the most preferred shopping market of Kanpur city. Sisamau is a mixed-commercial market area (not as per master plan but due to old residential plots of area) which makes it both market and residential area. Streets are usually congested because of illegal street parking and heavy pedestrian movement.

Figure 11: Sisamau market

Study Area

Figure 12: Busy street of Sisamau market

Source: Primary Survey

Figure 13: Shopping street in Sisamau market

Source: Primary Survey

3.4.4 Study area 4: Govind nagar

Govind nagar is located in the south of Kanpur city. It is also one of the most popular apparel market of the city because of its vicinity to most densely populated areas. It solely serves the southern part of city. It is also a mixed-commercial market area. It is located in ward no. 91 & 93. Kanpur city as always developed in southern direction due to the constraint of river Ganges in north. Govind nagar bears a huge share of population and area because of it. There is a need to develop more markets in southern part.

Figure 14: A busy street in Govind nagar

Source: Primary Survey

Figure 15: Shopping street in Govind nagar

Source: Primary Survey

Figure 16: Illegal street parking in Govind nagar

Source: Primary Survey

Kanpur city is major commercial hub among all the urban areas of Uttar Pradesh. Kanpur city serves for all the shopping purpose for nearby cities. But still new market areas are not being developed by the Government. Kanpur city has undergone through major infrastructure development in JNNURM and Kanpur city is also selected under AMRUT for development. There is a need for developing new market areas in the city. A general observation can be coined that new market areas should be developed in southern side of city because of huge population density (which is further increasing) available. It will reduce the distance travelled by consumers' for shopping activities.

CHAPTER 4: DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The data analysis has been structured in a way to provide a comprehensive view of the entire study area on the existing aspects and to direct the framework of the discussion towards the points. The first objective starts with ascertaining the factors for choosing retail store location by retailers. It consists of two research questions. One of them is identifying the factors retailers consider when making a location selection decision in India. Second research question is about recognizing the problems faced by retailers for choosing retail store location and coping strategies they follow for it.

A store's location is one of the most important decisions a retailer must make, as it typically involves substantial financial outlay and long-term commitment. In Indian scenario, most of the cities are seeing an organic growth. Due to unavailability of proper technical and socio-economical understanding many new areas are planned and many new commercial areas are planned in suburbs which ultimately merges into city limits after some years. Huge migration towards urban areas also put pressure on urban amenities and commercial areas. There is a need to locate these urban centres and amenities strategically.

However second objective is to select the relevant factors for identifying suitable retail location in Indian cities. The research question talks about how various techniques can be used as an effective tool for locating a retail store in most efficient way. For the study literature review was done to select the suitable parameters and variables. Many factors were taken from earlier proposed theories in the field and were modified according to the need of study. While sorting these factors were majorly categorized into two categories. While surveying some focus group discussions and experts meetings were conducted. Here are some views of experts for potential commercial location decision-

“A new potential location identification is the major determining factor of success of store. Many factors define the success of stores but location is the most important.”

- Mr. Ajay Singh, Head of traders association, Sisamau

“Usually retailers try to find location for a new store near the existing market as these markets as well recognized and shopping attractions lead people to the existing markets which can be a strategic factor to remember.”

- Mr. Ramdayal Yadav, Zonal manager of Cotton County, Kanpur

“People don’t want to travel too far from their homes and want the quality products at their doorstep. Now many online cloth selling websites are in market. To compete we always prefer the consumer preference over other factors.”

- Mr. Aslam Murtaza, A shopkeeper in Naveen Market

Table 5: Variables and parameters of study

<u>Variables</u>	<u>Parameters</u>
Demography (within distance of 1km. , 3 km. and 5 km. and above)	Population density of target population
	Average monthly spending
	Education level
Transportation	Available parking space
	Distance from nearest public transport node
	Distance travelled to reach store
Store specific competition	No. of available staff
	Availability of competitive space
	Availability of loading/unloading space
Economic	Store aesthetics
	Shopping satisfaction

Figure 17: Major factors identified for study

4.1 Data Collection

Data collection process included both primary and secondary surveys. Primary survey was distributed into two different categories: Consumer survey and Shopkeeper survey. Shopkeeper survey was done to fulfill the objective 1 and to identify the suggested potential locations within city. These suggested potential location will be used to check the difference from identified location with the help of analysis.

Consumer survey was done to identify the travel and spending behavior of users for shopping purpose. It also included the market places they visit, frequency of visit, mode of commute, Distance travelled, parking availability, Average monthly spending and suggested nearest potential location for new stores.

4.1.1 Sampling Strategy

Sampling strategy for both shopkeeper's survey and consumer's survey will be random sampling method.

Sample size is found out as follows:

$$N = t^2 \times p (1 - p) / m^2 \quad \text{where,}$$

N= required sample size,

t = confidence level at 95% (standard value of 1.96)

p = estimated no. of people residing within buffer of 1 km. of market area

m = margin of error at 5% (standard value of 0.05)

Table 6: Populations of study area

Area	Ward	Population
General ganj	102	25030
Naveen market	59	27687
Sisamau	41,50	39034
Govind nagar	93,98	47230

Total Population size = 1,55,328

Confidence level = 95%

Sample size = 383

This sample size was distributed between consumers and shopkeepers survey. Surveys⁴ were conducted for a week in February, 2017.

⁴ Survey formats are in annexures.

4.2 Analysis of identified factors

Many factors were taken from earlier proposed theories in the field and were modified according to the need of study. While sorting these factors were majorly categorized into two categories –

- a) **Operative factors-** Factors involved in operating a location
- b) **Market Factors-** Factors involved in implications of store attraction

4.2.1 Operative Factors

Operating factors are the factors which are involved in operating a location. Operating factors are usually financial factors. Operating factors can vary from one location to other effecting the location decision as the investment can differ in different location. Operative factors include registration cost, circle rate/rental cost of area, salaries and other store operating costs, loading/unloading costs if any applicable.

Table 7: No. of shops registered and employees

Area	Shops registered	Employees
Generalganj	147	376
Naveen Market	42	135
Sisamau	79	210
Govind Nagar	29	90

Source: Labour court office -3, Kanpur

Registration fee for a shop: According to U.P. Dookan aur Vanijya Adhistan Act, 1962, a shop having 1-5 employees should pay 200 Rs. per financial year as registration fee to local body.

Table 8: Circle rates of study area markets

Area	Circle rate per sq. m. (Commercial land)
Generalganj	46,000 Rs.
Naveen Market	55,000 Rs.
Sisamau	45,000 Rs.
Govind Nagar	40,000 Rs.

Source: Kanpur Land Rates (Mulyankan Suchi, Kanpur Nagar)

According to available data, Registration fee is a constant fee to paid per year but Circle rate varies throughout the city, so it is a variable cost for analysis and the amount of circle rate is huge compared to other costs. Circle rate also plays an important role while choosing a new potential site for establishing a new store.

4.2.2 Market factors

Market factors are the factors which include consumers, competition, nearby available services, surrounding population and spending habits of consumers. These factors are involved in implications for store attractions. These market factors are helpful for predicting the success of store in the market. For study purpose, market factors are categorized into three major categories-

- 1) Relating to customers
 - a) Population Density
 - b) Spending Habits
 - c) Purchasing Power
 - d) Education Level
- 2) Relating to other facilities
 - a) Distance of market from distance
 - b) Availability of parking space
 - c) Availability of public transport
- 3) Relating to competitors
 - a) No. of registered shops
 - b) Availability of competitive space
 - c) No. of available staff

4.2.2.1 Shopkeeper's survey

Shopkeeper's survey was conducted in two phases. First phase included the primary survey while visiting the markets. Major focus of primary survey was to understand the factors retailers use while identifying a potential retail location. Second phase included focus group discussion and meetings with experts. In this way, objective 1 was fulfilled with the primary survey, FGD's and expert opinions.

Figure 18: Problems faced by shopkeepers in market

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: Nearly 40% of shopkeepers identified unavailability of loading/unloading space as a major problem they face while taking decisions for a new store.

Figure 19: Strategies used by shopkeepers in market

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: Most of the shopkeepers agreed that they prefer customer choices and vicinity of existing market area as the strategic parameters over other parameters.

4.2.2.2 Consumer's survey

Consumer's survey was conducted with focus of understanding the consumer's shopping behavioral characteristics. Consumer's survey included questions related to average shopping frequency of customers, average distance travelled by consumers for shopping, average monthly expenditure by consumers on shopping, preferred market areas for shopping and other related points.

Figure 20: Average shopping frequency of consumers

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: Most of the consumers do shopping on monthly basis or yearly. Shops usually try many marketing techniques and offers to attract customers.

Figure 21: Average distance travelled by Consumers for shopping

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: A huge share of customers travel minimum 3-5 km. and beyond for shopping purpose. If shopping places are located near to them it will save travel time and money effectively.

Figure 22: Average money spent by Consumers for shopping (monthly)

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: Major share of consumers spend 500 to 1500 Rs. per month but all these 3 categories are near to equal. It shows that all low-end, medium-end and high-end clothing stores are similarly required.

Figure 23: Market preferences by consumers for shopping

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: Most of the consumers chose Sisamau market area as preferred market area due to its connectivity of public transport and Naveen market is selected on 2nd place because of on-street parking facility available there.

4.2.2.3 Co-relation analysis

In the present study, Correlation analysis has been made in order to have an idea about the degree and direction of the relationship between the two variables under study. However, it fails to reflect upon the cause and effect relationship between the variables. In a bivariate distribution, if the variables have the cause and effect relationship, they are bound to vary in sympathy with each other and, therefore, there is bound to be a high degree of correlation between them. In other words, causation always implies correlation.

Scatterplot diagram is one of the simplest ways of diagrammatic representation of a bivariate distribution and provides us one of the simplest tools of ascertaining the correlation between two variables. Suppose we are given n pair of values $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ of two variables X and Y . For example, if the variables X and Y demote the height and weight respectively, then the pairs $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ may represent the heights and weights (in pairs) of n individuals. These n points may be plotted as dots (.) on the x -axis and y -axis in the xy -plane. (It is customary to take the dependent variable along the y -axis and independent variable along the x -axis.) The diagram of dots so obtained is known as scatter diagram. From scatter diagram we can form a fairly good, though rough, idea about the relationship between the two variables.

In this present study, Scatter diagram has been drawn as follows:

Relation between frequency of shopping and distance:

Scatterplot was drawn for identifying the relation between frequencies of shopping with average distance travelled by consumers for shopping.

Figure 24: Scatterplot for frequency and distance travelled by consumers

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: From the sample survey, it can be observed that frequency is decreasing as the distance for commute is increasing. It can be said that frequency and distance are inversely related.

Relation between Average expenditure and distance:

Scatterplot was drawn for identifying the relation between average monthly spending with average distance travelled by consumers for shopping.

Figure 25: Scatterplot for average monthly spending and distance travelled by consumers

Source: Primary Survey

Inference: From the sample survey, it can be observed that average monthly expenditure is increasing as the distance for commute is increasing. It can be said that frequency and distance are directly related. It can safely said that consumers do more shopping when they commute more distance.

Correlation among identified variables from consumers’ survey:

The variables identified from consumers’ survey to study the correlation are – **Distance travelled by consumers for shopping, Shopping frequency, Average monthly spending**⁵. There were 2 different scenarios created while manipulating the distance travelled by the consumers. While the dependency of shopping frequency and average monthly spending were” assumed as depending variable for distance⁶ travelled as an independent variable.

⁵ Average monthly spending here implies the average monthly amount of money spent by the consumers on apparels only. No other monthly commodity spending were accounted in survey.

⁶ Distance are categorized in 3 categories – 1 km, 3 km., 5 km. for the convenience of survey as well as identifying the primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas.

Scenario 1: If the average distance travelled by the consumers' is more than 3 km. (secondary trade areas) then, impact on the shopping frequency of consumer and the average monthly spending.

Scenario 2: If the average distance travelled by the consumers' is less than 3 km. (secondary trade areas) then, impact on the shopping frequency of consumer and the average monthly spending.

Results from scenario 1 are as follows:

If, Distance travelled increases then, Shopping frequency decreases and average monthly spending increases.

Distance \propto (1/Shopping frequency) \propto Average monthly spending

Results from scenario 2 are as follows:

If, Distance travelled decreases then, Shopping frequency increases and average monthly spending increases.

Distance \propto Shopping frequency \propto Average monthly spending

While, these two scenarios were analyzed for the collected consumers' data. Scenario 2 came out as a prominent scenario in study areas which clearly shows that consumers prefers to less travel for shopping and spend more while travelling less distance. It clearly implements that retail stores should be located near to residential areas. But in study area, most of the consumers have to travel more than 3 km. and beyond which should be reduced. This will also increase revenue for retailers. It will be a win-win situation for both consumers' and retailers'.

Further analysis is done on ArcMap software by preparing maps. The analysis will be done according to the earlier developed framework which is as follows-

Framework for identification of potential apparel retail location

4.3 Preparation of maps for analysis

The major part of analysis in this study includes the preparation of maps with the help of collected and analyzed data. These maps will serve as base for final overlay analysis which will identify the potential areas for locating commercial spaces to accommodate the demand of consumers and the retailers' revenue properly.

With the help of existing data (primary and secondary) four major maps were prepared-

1. Trade area buffer map for markets
2. Thiessen polygon (population) map
3. Landuse map of Kanpur Nagar (with existing master plan)
4. Circle rates map for city

Trade area buffer analysis map is prepared with the help of existing markets areas and their buffer is prepared in ArcMap with help of multi-buffer function. Three different buffers are drawn around the existing market areas (1 km. buffer, 3 km. buffer, 5km. buffer) to identify their primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas.

Thiessen polygon map is prepared for showing the equitable share of population over all four study area markets. This is prepared with existing algorithm in the ArcMap. It asks for the boundary for which the distribution is to be done (for this study it is municipal boundary) and the population for all the areas in the city is asked which is given as ward wise population.

Landuse map is prepared with the help of existing Master Plan of Kanpur, 2021. Existing master plan covers all the proposed landuses for year 2021. It guides for the existing locations of commercial areas. This helps to give these commercial locations lesser preference for finding potential as they are already existing markets.

Circle rates map is prepared with the help of data available on existing circle rates decided by the development authority. It differs from one place to another place. It is generally higher near commercial spaces. Its information allows the retailer to identify a location which satisfies his budget.

Thiessen polygon map is prepared for distributing the population share citywide with respect to the existing market places' trade areas. This will show the population distribution share for existing study area markets.

Figure 26: Thiessen polygon (population) map

The Thiessen Population map prepared on ArcMap 10.4 takes population distribution into account citywide. It does so with the help of wardwise population available from Census of India, 2011. For the study four study areas were selected so there are four polygons prepared in Thiessen (population) polygon map. Each polygon shows the concentration of population it caters within municipal limits.

Trade area buffer maps are created with the help of boundaries of existing market areas. These existing market boundaries should be drawn in Arcmap and other vicinity areas should be clearly identified before drawing it. The limits of primary, secondary and tertiary trade areas should be clearly defined. In this study, Primary trade area is identified as 1km. vicinity of market areas and likewise 3 km. for secondary trade areas and 5km. for tertiary trade areas from literature review.

Figure 27: Trade area buffer for markets

Trade area buffer map is prepared with the buffer of existing study area markets. The buffer distances are considered with the help of literature review. From literature review, 1 km. is considered as primary trade area which serves 50-80% customers of store. 3 km. is considered as secondary trade area which serves 15-25% of customers of store. 5 km. and beyond is considered as tertiary trade area which serves 5-10% consumers of the store. Trade area buffer is prepared with the help of multibuffer function in ArcMap. It considers all the centre points and then asks for different buffer distances.

Landuse map of the city can be prepared with the help of existing master plan of the city. The landuse map shows the predefined commercial spaces within city and its connectivity to other landuses. In this way the existing commercial area provide a base for other places where new commercial spaces will be viable and support the study.

Figure 28: Landuse map of Kanpur Nagar

Landuse map is prepared with the help of existing Master Plan of Kanpur, 2021 which is still in force. In landuse map all the types of proposed uses are provided. It guides for the existing locations of commercial areas. This helps to give these commercial locations lesser preference for finding potential as they are already existing markets. It also provides information about the prohibited areas within city which will be helpful to eliminate which analyzing the potential locations for new stores.

Circle rates map can be prepared with the help of circle rates handbook from development authority or the municipality. This should also be prepared for the complete city areas and the land with moderate prices should be selected to give a higher ranking than land with very high cost. This reduces the operative factor variable land cost and make a new retail store more affordable for retailer.

Figure 29: Circle rates map

Circle rates map is prepared with the help of data available on existing circle rates decided by the development authority. It differs from one place to another place. It is generally higher near commercial spaces. Its information allows the retailer to identify a location which satisfies his budget.

4.4 Weighted Overlay analysis:

For the study weighted overlay analysis was performed in ArcMap 10.4 software by ESRI. The Weighted Overlay tool applies one of the most used approaches for overlay analysis to solve multi-criteria problems such as site selection and suitability models. In a weighted overlay analysis, each of the general overlay analysis steps are followed. In weighted overlay analysis, you must define the problem, break the model into submodels, and identify the input layers.

The Weighted Overlay tool allows to implement several of the steps in the general overlay analysis process within a single tool. The tool combines the following steps:

- a) Reclassifies values in the input rasters into a common evaluation scale of suitability or preference, risk, or some similarly unifying scale
- b) Multiplies the cell values of each input raster by the rasters' weight of importance
- c) Adds the resulting cell values together to produce the output raster

The tool only accepts integer rasters as input, such as a raster of land use or soil types. Continuous (floating-point) rasters must be reclassified to integer before they can be used. The values of continuous rasters are grouped into ranges, such as for slope, or Euclidean distance outputs. Each range must be assigned a single value before it can be used in the Weighted Overlay tool.

The Reclassify tool allows for such rasters to be reclassified. You can either leave the value assigned to each range and assign weights to the cell values in the Weighted Overlay tool later, or you can assign weights at the time of reclassifying. With the correct evaluation scale chosen, simply add the raster to Weighted Overlay. The cells in the raster will already be set according to suitability or preference, risk, or some similarly unifying scale. The output rasters can be weighted by importance and added to produce an output raster.

This study practices various market and operating factors. Weighted overlay analysis used 4 different raster and assigned weightages to the features in it. These raster are

- a) Trade area buffer analysis (1km. , 3 km. , 5km. buffers fro study area markets)
- b) Thiessen polygon (Population) analysis
- c) Landuse analysis (Commercial area concentration)
- d) Circle rate analysis (City wide)

Figure 30: Weighted overlay map for commercial areas

Table 9: Scale values for Suitability (Weighted) analysis

Raster	% Influence	Field	Scale Value
Buffer Analysis	25%	1 km. buffer	1
		3 km. buffer	2
		5 km. buffer	3
		Other uses	3
Pop. Sum Thiessen	25%	4,32,098	3
		8,08,507	2
		8,63,648	2
		16,44,462	1
Land Rates	25%	0-25,000	2
		25,001-32,000	1
		32001-42,000	1
		42,001-55,000	3
		Restricted	Restricted
Landuse	25%	Commercial	1
		Residential	2
		Industrial	3
		PSP	2
		Transport	3
		Recreation	2
		Infrastructure	3
		Special Areas	Restricted

In the prepared weighted overlay map, the amalgamation of various variables is done with the help of overlay analysis method in ArcMap. These variables can be accounted for the ratio of influence that they have on the final outlay. For this study the ratio of influence is equally distributed among all four maps as in 25% weight to each map and its variables. The fields show the variables which are to be given scale value from 1 to 3 according to its priority or the likeliness. These all scale values are given to prepare the final overlay map with prepared rasters.

The final overlay maps contains only 4 categories. These 3 categories are- Areas which are most potential, areas with moderate potential and areas with least potential and last category is areas which are restricted for any kind of development. These areas include cantonment or some govt. lands which are strictly prohibited for other uses than prescribed. This will help for delineating the boundaries of areas and its potential.

Chapter 5: RECOMMENDATIONS

This kind of studies can only be successful if the planning interventions are added to it. This study is done to understand how the urban economics works and how small interventions can make greater changes to it. The implementation strategy for it should be developed at local level by the planning authorities. However an optional implementation strategy is also proposed which can be helpful but it should be modified according to the locations and other factors governing.

After identifying the potential of an area for developing retail stores, planning authorities can prepare legal interventions (like byelaws and interventions in master plan) which will help developing the areas by providing services near the residential areas. This will help prepare a more inclusive approach master plan.

Presently many cities are facing problem of land scarcity which could also become a problem in this case. So, it is recommended that this type of commercial development (inside residential areas) can be developed in government land (vacant patches) available, reconstruction of dilapidated buildings and / or alongside multi-use destinations (like nearby public places, transport nodes etc.).

A separate department should be constituted within municipality or development authority or local planning authority which will work for identifying and developing new commercial areas. This department can also be functioning for all the permissions and development strategies for potential commercial areas.

Retail based real estate transactions are based on the metric (prepared with the help of set of variables) and priced accordingly. A site with more facilities is more appreciated than a site with less facilities available.

There should be a provision of development supporting ancillary activities which will generate more consumers for the commercial area. This will help generate an induced increase in land rate around the surroundings. It will help increase municipal revenues as the municipality can now impose development impact fee to the people residing in surrounding areas.

The development process of new retail spaces will require large investments to be done by the municipality. Massive capital expenditure will be required for providing

new infrastructure and services in newly identified potential areas. There should be some methods for recovery of this type of capital expenditure. A suggested measure for the recovery of this type of investments can be “Land value capture”. It will help increase the revenues for municipality. (National Institute of Urban Affairs, 2016)

Land value capture relates to the recovery of a share of the increase in land values because of the positive externalities from activities other than investments done by the land owner. The increase in land value occurs due to governing changes, investments made in public infrastructure that increases quality of life and other services like transportation or social benefits and development of commercial, cultural, institutional, or residential development in the neighborhood.

All these changes are connected with increases in land prices of the affected properties without any extra effort of the land owner. The land owners in the vicinity of these changes become indirect yet rent seeking recipients of an “unearned increment”. The potential for dividend gains encourages projected investments in lands in urban areas and its surroundings.

The most common strategy to capture value created by investment externalities is through different forms of taxation. They include development charges, impact fees, or higher building fees. One of the techniques is Impact fee.

Impact fees are imposed, apart from the development taxes, on new developments in an area where a large new public investment has been declared. Such investments could include major roads and highways, commercial area development, metro rail, industrial corridors, ports, airports, and any other public infrastructure facility. They are levied to recover at least a share of the investment made. The impact fees generally vary depending on the location and the land use. It is collected when the landowner applies for new construction permission. (National Institute of Urban Affairs, 2016)

Impact fees are calculated based on the total cost of the project investment proposed and the development potential within the influence area. To this extent they are unique for each project area and would require a project-wise notification. They differ from development fee in so far as they are generally used to finance specific large new infrastructure projects, and not basic civic utility services.

An example of impact fee is the levy on new developments within the 1 km wide Growth Corridor (GC) on both sides of the 162 km Outer Ring Road (ORR) around Hyderabad. The impact fees were higher for the part of the corridor within the ORR and for commercial uses, and increases with building height. Impact fees have become an important component of municipal infrastructure finance in growth areas of developing cities.

Specifically in relation to retailing, the development plan must be:

- Evidence-based through supporting analysis and data to guide decision making;
- Consistent with the approach of these guidelines; and
- Clear and concise with regard to specific objectives and requirements.

Master plans and other city development plans should therefore-

1. Set out strategic guidance on the location and scale of retail development to support the citywide demand by identifying appropriate sites which are suitable and available and which match the future retailing needs of different areas of the city.
2. **Identify sites** which can accommodate the needs of modern retail formats in a way that maintains the essential character of the shopping area
3. Include objectives to support action initiatives in city and town centres; such as
 - Mobility management measures that both improve accessibility of retail areas while aiming to develop a pedestrian and cyclist friendly urban environment and vibrant street life; and
 - Public realm interventions aimed at improving the retailing experience through high quality civic design, provision of attractive street furnishing, lighting and effective street cleaning/business improvement district type initiatives; and
4. Identify relevant **development management criteria** for the assessment of retail developments in accordance with the prepared guidelines by planning authorities.
5. Planning authorities should balance quantitative estimates of future demand for retail floorspace of development plans, when assessing applications for new or expanded retail development with considerations in regard to vibrancy, choice, vitality and other qualitative issues.

Recommendations

A general statement of additional retail development requirements, reflecting the local evidence of market interest and the need to provide good opportunities for retail provision to serve the main population centres in the city, ought to be sufficient in order to formulate appropriate policies and criteria for dealing with new development proposals.

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ANNEXTURE

Annexure-A: Survey format for Shopkeeper's Survey

Question 1: What is Your Name?

Question 2: What is your age?

Question 3: What is your education level?

Question 4: Location of survey market area.

Question 5: Does market have sufficient loading/unloading space for shops? (Y/N)

Question 6: How many employees do work in your shop? (No. of employees)

Question 7: What are the problems that you face in the existing markets?

Question 8: What are the strategies that you follow while considering for a new potential retail location?

Question 9: Do you suggest any potential location for establishing new retail store, if any?

Question 10: Are you willing to shift or open a new store in the suggested location, if all the problems are resolved in new location? (Y/N)

Annexure-B: Survey format for Consumer's Survey

Question 1: What is Your Name?

Question 2: What is your age?

Question 3: What market places you visit (preferably)?

Question 4: What is your frequency of market visit for shopping?
(Weekly/Monthly/Quarterly or Yearly)

Question 5: What is your average distance of travel for shopping of clothes? (1 km., 3km., 5km. and beyond)

Question 6: Does your preferable market area has parking facility available? (Y/N)

Question 7: What is your average monthly expenditure for shopping of clothes?

Question 8: Do you suggest any potential location for developing new retail stores for your convenience, if any?
